

Corrigendum

Since the submission of this Master thesis and the writing of a subsequent report, some implementation details and information have been updated. The following is a list of all the differences between this thesis and the updated report¹ that must be considered when reading this work.

- p. 37 & p. 74: From later email conversation it is clear that the original authors only used the WEKA GUI and never the Java API.
- p. 72: The mistake of using 100 seconds instead of 120 has been since fixed in the code and all analyses were rerun. For updated results please refer to the updated report.
- p. 74: For the updated report all machine learning steps were implemented in Java code and no steps were conducted in the WEKA GUI.
- p. 78: For the updated report the Jupyter notebook was replaced by a plain Python script ("Feature Calculation and Normalization.py").
- p. 85-87: Time window comparison was carried out using simple cross-validation. It is not representative of the nested-cross validation results from the updated report. For a correct time window comparison, refer to the updated report.
- p. 87-88: This report uses the majority class share as a baseline, instead of the cross-validation results of a ZeroR (i.e., majority classifier). This mistake has been corrected in the updated report.
- Tables 13, 14, and 15: Display the results based on the validation using all the above-mentioned mistakes (wrong baseline length for normalization, simple cross-validation, wrong classification baseline). For correct results, consult Tables 2 and 3 in the updated report.
- p. 88-90 Section 7.2.3: After nesting the feature choice inside the cross-validation, this analysis of selected features is not accurate anymore and obsolete.
- p. 95 Section 8: Nested cross-validation was implemented for the updated report.
- p. 95 Section 8.1.1: Nested cross-validation was in fact used in the original study as the validation method. For a more accurate discussion on the threats to validity concerning the small sample sizes, please refer to the updated report.

¹The "updated report" refers to the manuscript submitted to ESEM 2024 which references this work.

Interruptibility of Software Developers and Its
Prediction Using Psycho-Physiological Sensors:
A Replication

September 24, 2023

Abstract

Context Interruptions at inopportune moments can negatively affect the perceived productivity of knowledge workers. To minimize interruptions at such moments, previous research has attempted to predict the interruptibility of knowledge workers using psycho-physiological sensors, with reportedly promising results. However, in the context of the replication crisis, previous results may not always be replicable. Furthermore, the process of replication is not straightforward, and replicators face a number of challenges.

Objective Firstly, we are interested in replicating the results of a study, that predicted the interruptibility of software developers with a high accuracy in lab settings and field settings. Secondly, since the original study lacks a replication package, we want to rebuild one as closely as possible to facilitate future replications. Finally, we want to report the lessons learned from replicating an existing study without replication packages.

Method We replicate the lab study methodology of the original study. As such, we conduct ten one-on-one sessions. The participants are asked to perform three code change tasks during a 60-minute programming session, while being frequently interrupted by a tablet application which surveys their perceived interruptibility, mental workload and the disruptiveness of the interruption. At the same time psycho-physiological data are being collected via the use of various sensors. These data are processed and used in machine learning models to predict the surveyed interruptibility rating. The resulting models are validated using repeated cross-validation and the performance is reported as the average accuracy across all cross-validation runs. Finally, post-interviews query the participants about their experiences with interruptions and about desired tool support that could help with unwanted interruptions.

Results We cannot replicate the originally observed accuracy of over 90%. Furthermore, we identify three serious threats to validity in both the original and our replication study; 1) overestimation of true accuracy due to small sample size and overfitting, 2) the problematic use of accuracy in a highly unbalanced data set and 3) the arbitrary method used to reduce the five-state Likert scale to two states. We also fail to observe the high correlations between interruptibility, mental workload and disruptiveness, reported in the original study. Finally, we provide a replication package to support future

replications and report lessons learned from replicating an existing study without a replication package.

Conclusions Due to the severity of the threats to validity identified, we believe that neither study is able to provide convincing evidence for the predictive power of psycho-physiological data. This conclusion would hold even if we were able to reproduce similar results, which we were not able to do. Thus, these threats will need to be addressed in future replications. The failure to replicate the correlations between interruptibility, mental workload and disruptiveness of interruptions may be attributed to several contextual deviations (e.g. participant profile, notification sound chosen. The interviews revealed a need for tools that reduce the impact of interruptions caused by notifications and chat messages. Finally, our lessons learned include problems with finding participants, how more thorough pilot sessions which are critical of the original study design could have caught problems earlier, and finally the problem of tacit knowledge transfer in email communication.

Zusammenfassung

Kontext Unterbrechungen zu unpassenden Zeitpunkten können sich negativ auf die wahrgenommene Produktivität von Wissensarbeitern auswirken. Um Unterbrechungen in solchen Momenten zu minimieren, haben frühere Forschungsarbeiten versucht, die Unterbrechbarkeit von Wissensarbeitern mit Hilfe psychophysiologischer Sensoren vorherzusagen, mit scheinbar vielversprechenden Ergebnissen. Im Zusammenhang mit der Replikationskrise sind vorherige Ergebnisse jedoch möglicherweise nicht immer replizierbar. Darüber hinaus ist der Prozess der Replikation nicht einfach, da die Replikatoren mit einer Reihe von Herausforderungen konfrontiert sind.

Ziel Erstens sind wir daran interessiert, die Ergebnisse einer Studie zu replizieren, die die Unterbrechbarkeit von Softwareentwicklern mit hoher Genauigkeit im Labor und im Feld vorhersagte. Zweitens wollen wir, da die ursprüngliche Studie kein Replikationspaket enthält, ein solches so genau wie möglich nachbilden, um zukünftige Replikationen zu erleichtern. Schließlich wollen wir über die Erfahrungen berichten, die wir bei der Replikation einer bestehenden Studie ohne Replikationspaket gemacht haben.

Methodik Wir replizieren die Methodik der ursprünglichen Laborstudie. Dazu führen wir zehn Einzelsitzungen durch. Die Teilnehmer werden gebeten, während einer 60-minütigen Programmiersitzung drei Code-Änderungen auszuführen, währenddessen werden sie häufig über eine Tablet-Anwendung unterbrochen werden, die ihre wahrgenommene Unterbrechbarkeit, geistige Arbeitsbelastung und die Störung durch die Unterbrechung erfasst. Gleichzeitig werden mit Hilfe verschiedener Sensoren psychophysiologische Daten erhoben. Diese Daten werden verarbeitet und in Machine-Learning-Modellen zur Vorhersage der erhobenen Unterbrechbarkeitswerte verwendet. Die resultierenden Modelle werden durch wiederholte Cross-Validation validiert und die Leistung wird als durchschnittliche Genauigkeit über alle Cross-Validationsläufe berichtet. Abschließend werden die Teilnehmer in Post-Interviews zu ihren Erfahrungen mit Unterbrechungen und der gewünschten Tool-Unterstützung befragt, welche bei unerwünschten Unterbrechungen helfen könnte.

Ergebnisse Wir können die ursprünglich beobachtete Genauigkeit von über 90% nicht wiederholen. Darüber hinaus stellen wir sowohl in der Original- als auch in der Replikationsstudie drei ernsthafte Bedrohungen für die Validität fest: 1) Überschätzung der tatsächlichen Genauigkeit aufgrund kleiner Stichprobengrößen und Überanpassung, 2) die problematische Verwendung der

Genauigkeit in einem stark unausgewogenen Datensatz und 3) die willkürliche Methode zur Reduzierung der fünfstufigen Likert-Skala auf zwei Stufen. Wir können auch nicht die hohen Korrelationen zwischen Unterbrechbarkeit, mentaler Arbeitsbelastung und Störung feststellen, die in der ursprünglichen Studie berichtet wurden. Schließlich stellen wir ein Replikationspaket zur Verfügung, um zukünftige Replikationen zu fördern, und berichten über die Erfahrungen, die wir bei der Replikation einer bestehenden Studie ohne Replikationspaket gemacht haben.

Conclusio Aufgrund der Schwere der festgestellten Risiken für die Validität sind wir der Ansicht, dass keine der beiden Studien in der Lage ist, überzeugende Beweise für die Vorhersagekraft psychophysiologischer Daten zu liefern. Diese Schlussfolgerung würde auch dann gelten, wenn wir in der Lage wären, ähnliche Ergebnisse zu reproduzieren, was uns nicht gelungen ist. Daher müssen diese Risiken bei künftigen Reproduktionen berücksichtigt werden. Die fehlende Reproduzierbarkeit der Korrelationen zwischen Unterbrechbarkeit, mentaler Arbeitsbelastung und Störung durch Unterbrechungen kann auf verschiedene Abweichungen im Kontext zurückgeführt werden (z. B. Teilnehmerprofil, gewählter Benachrichtigungston). Die Interviews zeigten, dass ein Bedarf an Tools besteht, die die Auswirkungen von Unterbrechungen durch Benachrichtigungen und Chat-Nachrichten reduzieren. Schließlich haben wir gelernt, dass es Probleme bei der Suche nach Teilnehmern gibt, dass gründlichere Pilotsitzungen, die dem ursprünglichen Studiendesign gegenüber kritisch sind, Probleme früher hätten aufdecken können, und schließlich das Problem der impliziten Wissensübertragung in der E-Mail-Kommunikation.

Contents

1	Introduction	12
2	Background	14
2.1	Replication	14
2.1.1	Replication vs. Reproduction and Other Definitions . .	14
2.1.2	Need for Replication and the "Replication Crisis" . . .	16
2.1.3	Biases in Replications	17
2.1.4	Reporting Guidelines for Replications	18
2.1.5	Reporting Replication Results in Machine Learning . .	19
2.1.6	Laboratory Packages	20
2.2	Interruptibility Prediction and Biometric Sensors	23
2.2.1	EEG	24
2.2.2	Eye Tracking	24
2.2.3	ECG and BVP/PPG	25
2.2.4	EDA	25
2.2.5	Body Temperature	25
2.2.6	Sensor Combination	25
2.2.7	Interruption, Resumption and Edit Lag	25
3	Related Work	26
3.1	Replications in Empirical Software Engineering	26
3.2	Replications in Interruption Management	28
4	Original Study	28
4.1	Original Study - Research Questions	28
4.1.1	Main Research Question	28
4.1.2	Secondary Research Questions	29
4.2	Original Study - Participants	29
4.3	Original Study - Experiment Design	29
4.3.1	Project and Tasks	30
4.3.2	Simulated Interruptions	31
4.3.3	Follow-Up Interview	31
4.3.4	Data Pre-Processing	32
4.3.5	Building and Validating the Machine Learning Models	35
4.4	Original Study - Artifacts	36
4.4.1	Detailed Experiment Protocol	36
4.4.2	Document Explaining Hexagon Geometry	36
4.4.3	Fish Tank Movie	36
4.4.4	Project and Tasks: JHotDraw	37

4.4.5	Sensor Devices Used	37
4.4.6	Pre- and Post-Interview Questionnaires	37
4.4.7	Data	37
4.4.8	Source Code / Executable (Interruption App)	38
4.4.9	Source Code (Pre-Processing and Analysis)/ GUI Protocol (ML: Weka)	38
4.5	Original Study - Context Variables	38
4.6	Original Study - Summary of Results	41
4.6.1	Results of Interruptibility Prediction	42
4.6.2	Results of Time Window Choice	43
4.6.3	Results of Feature Choice	44
4.6.4	Results of Interruption Surveys	44
4.6.5	Follow-Up Interview Results	46
5	Experiment Design	47
5.1	Outline of the Replication Process	47
5.2	Experiment Design incl. Deviations from Original Study	51
5.2.1	Summary of Deviations	51
5.2.2	Finding Participants	52
5.2.3	Recreating Sensor Devices Setup	53
5.2.4	Recreating the Experiment Context	59
5.2.5	Recreating the Experiment Protocol	63
5.2.6	Recreating the Interruption App	67
5.2.7	Recreating the Data Processing	68
5.2.8	Recreating the Machine Learning Steps	73
5.3	Replication Package	77
6	Limitations	81
7	Experiment Results	84
7.1	Interruption Data	84
7.2	Model Performance	86
7.2.1	Time Windows Comparison	87
7.2.2	Two and Five States Interruptibility	88
7.2.3	Feature Choice	89
7.3	Interruptibility, Mental Load and Lags	91
7.4	Effectiveness of Negotiated Interruptions	92
7.5	Interruption Timing and Support	93

8	Threats to Validity	95
8.1	Internal Validity	96
8.1.1	Problems with Small Sample Size and Overfitting	96
8.1.2	Problems with Arbitrary Two-State Split	97
8.1.3	Problems With the Originally Reported “High Accuracy”	98
8.1.4	Compare with Follow-Up Study	98
8.2	Construct Validity	99
8.3	External Validity	100
9	Discussion	100
9.1	Results	100
9.1.1	Model Performance	100
9.1.2	Relevance of In-Person Interruption	101
9.1.3	Mental Load, Interruption Lag	101
9.1.4	Opportune Interruption Moments	102
9.1.5	Interruptibility and Disruptiveness	102
9.1.6	Distribution of Five-State Interruptibility	103
9.1.7	Predicting Adjacent Categories	103
9.2	Lessons Learned	103
10	Conclusion	109

Glossary

Anonymization The process of removing or disguising personally identifiable information in data to protect individual privacy.

Biometric Sensors Sensors that measure physiological or behavioral characteristics of individuals, such as heart rate or brain activity. Also referred to as "psycho-physiological sensors" when measuring psycho-physiological states.

Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN) A network of servers that stores R packages and provides them for download and installation.

Confidence Interval (CI) A statistical range around an estimate, showing the likely range of the true population parameter with a specified level of confidence. It helps measure the precision of findings and assesses uncertainty in the research results.

Context Variables Observed or controlled factors within the research environment that impact the study's outcomes, helping researchers manage variability and ensure study validity.

Dry and Wet Electrodes Types of electrodes used in EEG, with dry electrodes not requiring a conductive gel.

Effect Size "A quantitative reflection of the magnitude of some phenomenon that is used for the purpose of addressing a question of interest" [43, p. 140].

File Drawer Problem The tendency for studies with non-significant results to be hidden or filed away, leading to a biased representation of research outcomes.

Fixations Periods during which the eyes remain relatively still, focusing on a specific point of interest.

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) A European Union regulation that governs the processing of personal data and imposes strict rules on data protection and privacy.

Machine Learning (ML) "Machine learning (ML) is a branch of artificial intelligence that systematically applies algorithms to synthesize the underlying relationships among data and information" [7, p. 1].

Meta-Analysis A statistical technique that combines data and results from multiple studies to draw more robust conclusions.

Overfitting Occurs in machine learning when a model learns the training data too well, capturing noise and random fluctuations rather than the underlying patterns, leading to poor generalization to unseen data.

Prediction Interval (PI) "A statistical technique for predicting the range of effects that researchers should expect in a replication study. This technique respects both the variability in the original study and the variability in the replication study to come to a global view of whether the results of the two are consistent." [67].

Pseudonymization A data protection technique that involves replacing identifiable information with pseudonyms or codes, often reversible with access to a key.

Psycho-physiological States States of the body and mind, including emotions, cognitive load, and attention, that can be measured and analyzed using physiological sensors.

Publication Bias The tendency for studies with non-significant results to be underreported or not published, leading to an overrepresentation of significant results in the literature.

Pupil Dilation The expansion or contraction of the pupil in response to changes in lighting conditions or emotional arousal.

R Package A collection of functions and data sets in the R programming language, often used for sharing code and data.

Random Seed A starting value used in random number generation that determines the sequence of random numbers generated by a computer program.

Saccades Rapid eye movements that occur between fixations, allowing the eyes to shift their focus from one point to another.

Tacit Knowledge Transfer The transfer of knowledge that is difficult to express or document explicitly, often gained through experience.

Version Control A system that manages changes to documents, code, or other files, enabling tracking and collaboration on different versions.

1 Introduction

There have been a number of recent studies that have focused on studying developer productivity and well-being [84, 95, 29]. One particular area of interest is in fostering a highly productive state of deep focus, sometimes called "flow" in reference to the similar psychological state discovered by Csíkszentmihályi [25]. Studying software developer behavior, a recent study has observed how interruptions can have a negative effect by reducing the amount of time spent in deep focus, which in turn leads to diminished perceived productivity [58].

There have been attempts to reduce the effect of interruptions on workers' productivity by trying to build systems which reduce or reschedule interruptions (sometimes referred to as "interruption management systems") [95, 42, 56, 6, 45]. To accomplish this task, these systems must be able to distinguish between more and less opportune moments for interruptions. Therefore, previous research has focused on identifying opportune moments for interruptions and the (automated) prediction of interruptibility. In the past, prediction models have used contextual sensors (e.g. mouse and keyboard input), psycho-physiological sensors (e.g. heart beat sensors, eye tracking) or a combination of both. Even systems using very simple models have already proved to be effective in reducing unwanted interruptions, as observed in the FlowLight study [95]. More accurate models might further improve the effectiveness of such systems. In this regard, one promising study was performed in 2015 by Züger et al. which used psycho-physiological sensors to predict the interruptibility of software developers at relatively high accuracies of 91.5% in the lab and 78.6% in the field.

In our study, we aim to replicate these findings by replicating the lab study which is half of the original experiment. In the course of this lab study, 10 participants with prior software development experience work for 60 minutes on real-life code change tasks, while being frequently interrupted and asked about their perceived interruptibility. During this experiment, psycho-physiological sensors are being used to record data related to the participants' mental and physical state. These data are then used to predict interruptibility ratings that are simultaneously obtained. The original study also investigates a number of correlations previously observed in prior literature, such as the negative effect of high mental workload on interruptibility. Furthermore, short interviews explore the desire for tool support which could help developers to deal with interruptions. In our replication we also try to recreate the previously observed effects as well as the interview results.

The decision to replicate this lab study came down to two main factors. Firstly, the scope of the lab study with 10 participants and a controlled

experiment setup was manageable, given the limited time frame and resources of a master’s thesis project. Secondly, the original study is quite influential, having been cited in over 110 publications¹ in the time span of 8 years. Despite this fact, no close (external) replications of their findings exist. Furthermore, the original study lacks a replication package, which is important to promote replicability of empirical work [11]. Therefore, one of the contributions of this work will be to provide a replication package for this experiment aiming to encourage potential future replications.

In reviewing the literature on replicability, we found that previous work [11, 74, 57, 49] have focused on challenges of replicating studies with available replication packages. We believe that by replicating a study without such a package, we can discover new insights on challenges which arise during such a process. This is especially relevant, given the historically low rate of replication packages available (discussed in more detail in Section 3). We do recognize that replicating an experiment that is 8 years old already could be quite challenging, given the fast pace of changes in IT technology and literature. In fact, da Silva et al. even discusses the problem of the significant difference in time distance between replications and original studies when comparing internal ($0.8 \text{ Years} \pm 1.7$) and external replications ($4.8 \text{ Years} \pm 2.8$) [79]. However, discarding older studies without replication packages as not replicable by default, might be problematic for long term validity of our research field, which is why we believe that such replications are necessary despite these unique challenges. All in all, we believe that our insights could be valuable to other researchers trying to replicate older studies without replication packages.

We summarize the three goals of this study as follows:

1. Improve the validity of the original study by trying to answer the following question: *Can we replicate the original findings of predicting interruptibility with high accuracy using only biometric sensors?*
2. Provide a replication package for the original study encouraging future replications of this study.
3. Discover unique challenges which arise when replicating older studies (in the field of empirical software engineering) without replication packages.

Thesis Overview The next chapter provides more detailed background of our study and consists of two parts. The first half present background on replications. This includes necessary definitions, explaining the need

¹according to google scholar accessed on 18th of July 2023

for replication, and prior effort to improve replicability such as reporting guidelines and advocating the use of replication packages. The second half contains background on the of psycho-physiological sensors used in this experiment and their previous use to track various mental states related to interruptibility. Chapter three discusses related works of previous replications in the field of empirical software engineering and then more specifically replications in interruption management. Chapter four provides a summary of the original study. Chapter five explains the design of our replication including an overview and timeline of the replication process, the replicated experiment design presenting all deviations from the original design and finally an overview of the replication package. Chapter six discusses the limitations resulting from the deviations from the original study design. Chapter seven presents the replicated results and compares them with the original findings. Chapter eight presents the threats to validity we have identified and explains how we tried to mitigate them. In chapter nine, we discuss the replicated results and provide lessons learned during the replication process. Finally, chapter ten provides a conclusion of our work.

2 Background

2.1 Replication

2.1.1 Replication vs. Reproduction and Other Definitions

Unfortunately, the use of the words replication and reproduction is not as straightforward as one might assume. As such, in this subsection we will explicitly state the terminology used in this paper.

The varying uses and definitions of these two words have been discussed thoroughly by Barba [10]. She identifies the earliest use of these terms and finally recommends the definitions used by Claerbout, Donoho and Peng. These go as follows [10]:

1. **Reproducible research:** Authors provide all the necessary data and the computer codes to run the analysis again, re-creating the results.
2. **Replication:** A study that arrives at the same scientific findings as another study, collecting new data (possibly with different methods) and completing new analyses.

Therefore, while reproduction focuses on the strict repetition of all steps and exact repetition of observed results by an external group, replication

tries to recreate the findings by observing similar results in a different context (e.g. different data, subjects, sensors, etc.). They both serve very different functions in the scientific process. While reproduction double-checks the reliability of processes of the original study, replication is concerned with the generalizability of the observed findings. In other words, reproduction is more concerned with internal validity, while replication aims to improve external validity.

Shepperd et al. [73] arrive at a similar but slightly different definition of replication and reproduction, based on a previous taxonomy by Gómez et al. [31]. Gómez et al. groups replication studies into three groups:

1. Group I: Faithful replication or original experiment with no or minimal changes
2. Group II: Some variation from the original experiment
3. Group III: Sharing of the same constructs and hypotheses (aka "conceptual" replications")

Shepperd et al. then defines groups II and III as a continuum (rather than distinct categories) and defines reproduction as studies falling into group I and replications as studies falling anywhere between group II and III.

Although this distinction is important to make, no formal definitions have been imposed yet, and even recent replication/reproduction studies (e.g. [72]) seem to be using these terms interchangeably. Moreover, Barba identifies that a large number of publications use these terms switching their meanings when compared to the definitions provided by Claerbout/Donoho/Peng. In her work Barba mentions a more recent switch of these definitions used by the Association of Computing Machinery (ACM) on Result and Artifact Review and Badging. Since then, the ACM project has updated their terminology as a result of discussions with the National Information Standards Organization (NISO) and currently follow the predominant definitions as recommended by Barba [10, 1].

Additionally, both reproduction and replications can also be split into external and internal, where external studies are run with no (or minimal) involvement of the original authors [73]. Some commentators argue for the more independent external studies [16, 44], while others warn about the likelihood of deviating too much from the original study [75].

Some authors (e.g. [73, 52]), also strongly advise the replication to explicitly state the goal of replication clearly referencing the original study. By doing so they exclude studies labeled by other mapping studies as independent or conceptual replications. Mäntylä et al. argue that a broader definition would

be better to avoid underreporting of many studies they have identified as replications [54].

Adhering to these definitions **we classify our study as an external replication**. If we were to use Gómez et al.’s categorization we would most closely fall into **group II** as we tried to keep variations from the original experiment to a minimum. However, due to the lack of access to original hardware, data, code and an exact experiment protocol (as well as due to a previously planned extension) our replication was pushed more towards **group III** where certain aspects of the original study design could only be replicated conceptually (e.g. using functionally similar sensors, adapting interruption app to suit extension, etc.). Although we were in contact with the authors via e-mail, communication was limited to answering questions which arose during the replication. We do not consider this enough involvement to be considered an internal replication. Any decisions taken as a result of communication with the original authors are documented in this paper.

2.1.2 Need for Replication and the ”Replication Crisis”

One of the origins of the narrative that we are currently in a ”replication crisis” has to be the results of the Open Science Collaboration’s Reproducibility Project: Psychology [65]. While replicating 100 studies in the field of psychology, the researchers could only replicate significant findings for 36% of the studies. The narrative built from this result was that more than 60% of psychology research would not be replicable, putting the scientific process of the majority of research in doubt.

While such a statement would be shocking, a later study by Patil et al. [67] softened this claim, by reframing the expectations for replication studies. By viewing study results as samples drawn from a random distribution, they found that replications can report results without significant finding or with a different effect size (even including effect changing directions), without proving or disproving the validity of the original results. This is especially true, if the sample size and/or effect size of the studies are small. They have proposed that rather than focusing on significance or effect sizes and confidence intervals (CI), replications should consider prediction intervals (PI) instead. This interval is calculated based on effect size and sample size and sets more realistic goals for replication studies. By adopting prediction intervals in the Open Science project, they found that 77% of studies reported effect sizes inside the 95% prediction interval. This paints a very different picture than the original 36%. Rather than a majority of psychology research being not replicable, replication is possible, but the results of original studies with small sample sizes are rather uninformative in the sense that replication

results will vary more strongly.

While prediction intervals explain the variance of replication results, a more recent study by Santos et al. [71] asked if a single replication could reliably verify or disprove the results of a baseline study. To answer this question, they simulated replication results by drawing samples from a random distribution. The result of their research was that regardless of the statistic used (e.g. p-value, effect size, 95% CI, 95% PI) given a small enough sample size and/or effect size the comparison a single replication delivers is not reliable enough. The authors conclude their research by redefining the purpose of replications and original work, as being parts in a larger puzzle, that can only be reliably pieced together by meta-analysis.

While this may seem discouraging for carrying out replication studies (given their relatively small individual impact), the authors emphasize the increased need for replication as part of the bigger picture [71, p. 33]:

”First and foremost, however, we must learn how to encourage researchers to run replications in SE and raise awareness of how just important they are.”

On the other hand, Shepperd et al. warns researchers about replicating studies which are underpowered (small effect size, small sample size), as the replication results might still fall into the very wide prediction interval set by the original study without contributing much knowledge to answering the original question. Instead, they recommend redesigning the experiment or conducting a meta-analysis [73]. Meta-analysis pools together data and results of different papers.

2.1.3 Biases in Replications

However, original works still are prone to publication-bias, i.e. the problem of not significant results being considerably underreported. Although Shepperd et al. [73] acknowledge publication bias in their introduction, they do not discuss what impact this could have on meta-analyses pooling together results exclusively collected from original work. We would argue that this is still a strong point of replications, which have stronger incentives to be published regardless of the results, and therefore (at least in theory) should not suffer from the ”file drawer” problem to the same extent as original work.

While meta-analysis is desired, Runeson et al. [70] report difficulties in synthesizing such result in their attempt at pooling together the results of three related replications. They identify three factors, as to why it is hard to synthesize results: 1) Variations between experiments can have large effects on the outcomes making comparison difficult, 2) studies may be underpowered,

3) studies may have inherently bad experiment designs. Additionally, Silva et al. [79] identify a clear researcher bias, in which internal replications are far more confirmatory than their external counterparts, which again adds to the problems of interpreting replication results.

2.1.4 Reporting Guidelines for Replications

In their investigations regarding replication studies Magalhães et al. recommends the adoption of the reporting guidelines set out by Carver et al. They recommend specifically these guidelines as they are a good starting point, that has already been successfully tested in the past. As such this paper will follow these guidelines and include the following information [52, 17]:

1. Information about the original study to provide enough context for understanding the replication, including:
 - Research questions,
 - Participants,
 - Design,
 - Artifacts,
 - Context variables, and
 - Summary of results;
2. Information about the replication to help readers understand specific important details about the replication itself, including:
 - Motivation for replication,
 - Level of interaction with original experimenters, and
 - Changes to original experiment;
3. Comparison of replication results with original study results to illustrate commonalities and differences in the results obtained, including
 - Consistent results, and
 - Inconsistent results; and
4. Conclusions across studies to provide readers with important insights that can be drawn from the series of studies that may not be obvious from a single study.

Category	Information	Reference to Sections in this Paper
Original study	Research questions	Section 4.1
Original study	Participants	Section 4.2
Original study	Design	Section 4.3
Original study	Artifacts	Section 4.4
Original study	Context variables	Section 4.5
Original study	Summary of results	Section 4.6
Replication	Motivation for replication	Section 1
Replication	Level of interaction with original experimenters	Section 5.1
Replication	Changes to original experiment	Section 5.2
Replication Results	Consistent Results	Section 7
Replication Results	Inconsistent Results	Section 7
Conclusions Across Studies	Important Insights	Section 9

Table 1: Summary of mandatory information according to Carver et al.’s [17] reporting guidelines for replications and references to sections in this paper which cover these topics.

The first point will be covered in Section 4, where we summarize and present all the necessary information about the original study. The second point will be covered in Section 5, where we present the design of our replication, including all intentional and unintentional changes. The level of interaction with the original experimenters was briefly addressed in this section and will be covered in more detail in Section 5. The motivation for replication is explained in the introduction. The third point will be covered in Section 7. Lastly, the conclusion across studies will be discussed in Section 9.

2.1.5 Reporting Replication Results in Machine Learning

The previously stated information is based on replication in the fields of psychology, and empirical software engineering. The studies from these fields typically use classical statistics tools (e.g. null hypothesis significance testing) and report information typical for those tools (e.g. p-value, effect size, CI, PI). The set of metrics reported in machine learning (ML) studies differs

substantially from those classical metrics (e.g. accuracy, precision, recall, AUC, etc.). At the point of writing this paper, we could not find any guidance on which metrics should be reported for machine learning replications. Therefore, we decided to report all metrics found in the original paper as a minimal requirement for comparing the two studies.

Additionally, Beam et al. presents challenges which are unique to replication of machine learning studies namely [12]:

1. Enormous number of parameters
 - (a) Often set "silently" by using default settings
 - (b) Default settings might vary from one software/library version to another
2. Frequent use of randomness in ML methods (e.g. Random Forest, Repeated Cross Validation)
 - (a) Unless a specific seed number is specified for the pseudo-random code the system may default to a random seed which is hard to replicate (e.g. current time as random seed)
 - (b) Henderson et al. [35] found that changing this single number can lead to significantly different results

2.1.6 Laboratory Packages

In their work Basili et al. present the idea of conducting empirical research as "families of experiments" [11]. This concept sees original studies and (multiple) replications as one whole that can better capture the knowledge about a specific phenomenon. Furthermore, threats to validity of previous studies, can be counteracted by addressing them in the experiment design of future replications. To facilitate this approach, they advocate the use of lab packages. These packages capture all necessary information about the experiment:

- experimental design
- experiment artifacts
- experiment processes
- analysis methods
- motivation behind key design decisions

They argue that this facilitates reuse of experiment artifacts, which not only saves time and cost but also builds up knowledge about the use of a particular artifact.

At a minimum, these lab packages should enable reproduction, which (mostly) do not vary from the original procedures. In addition to this baseline requirement, Basili et al. mention four requirement levels:

1. Supporting replications which vary in procedures; by assisting experimenters in understanding and addressing threats to validity.
2. Supporting replications which vary in the hypotheses; by providing rationales for key experimental context decisions, and specifying in sufficient detail models for processes, effectiveness and context. Here detail is deemed sufficient when feasible changes can be identified and hypotheses can be made about their effects on the results.
3. Supporting conceptual replications; by linking together lab packages of related experiments, and by treating lab packages as "living documents" which are regularly updated to reflect the current understanding of the experiments they describe.
4. Supporting research community and replications in general; by forming groups of researchers aimed at facilitating replication (e.g. ISERN: the International Software Engineering Research Network).

The authors stress that research must be a collaborative activity, and that it is not realistic to have one perfect experiment in Software Engineering.

Following up on this research, Shull et al. [74] have conducted a number of replication studies, based on such lab packages. They discovered that despite their best efforts not every necessary detail can be captured at once in a lab package. They attribute this to the problem of tacit knowledge transfer. As a consequence, they advocate for adopting processes involving support from original research groups instead of relying solely on lab packages. More specifically, they recommend bi-annual meetings, possibly in a workshop environment. As a secondary means of communication, they propose close contact via e-mail. However, while e-mails are good for focused question, they do not facilitate both parties fully grasping the context of the experiment. In cases where close collaboration is not feasible, replications must define the experiment process and assess process conformance in regard to the original experiment.

Additionally, they recommend carrying out a pilot experiment prior to the full replication. This still requires some effort, but far less than the full

Figure 1: FIRE (Source: [57] p. 209)

replication. During this phase, problems with tacit knowledge transfer can be identified prior to the replication.

Moreover, after a replication is done, defects can be tracked in the lab package. Frequently occurring false positives (e.g. defects which are outside the scope of the experiment) should also be tracked. Existing artifacts may be updated based on the knowledge gained from replicating. The authors recommend having two versions of the lab package. A golden version, which is (nearly) perfect, and an oracle version, which is actually used in an experiment (including defects). All these updates to the lab package require some sort of version control and configuration management. The authors reference this as future work for the CeBASE project, which unfortunately at the time of writing does not seem to be accessible anymore.

Building on top of this research, Mendonça et al. [57] propose the Framework for Improving the Replication of Experiments (FIRE) (see Figure 1), which aims to facilitate carrying out groups of related replication studies.

Madeyski and Kitchenham present the idea of reproducible research (RR) as an extension of lab packages, where they define RR as seeing the product of research as the paper plus the computational environment. By using R and knitr they embed the computation steps into the paper itself via executable code cells. As for the data and methods, these are published as an R package

on CRAN, guaranteeing access and clear definitions of each method and data set [50].

Madeyski and Kitchenham also discuss two major objections to RR 1) *potential loss of intellectual property* and 2) *additional effort required by reproducible research*. For the first objection, they present licensing as a potential solution. For the second objection, they do agree that RR might produce considerable overhead deemed too large for some less critical disciplines in software engineering. However, they point out the risk of publishing more and more incorrect results without a systematic way of correcting them [50].

One additional problem they mention is *sharing of sensitive data*. They answer this objection by pointing at a tool, which can "anonymize" the data for the sharing process. However, our inspection of the tool revealed that it provides features for "pseudonymization" rather than "anonymization" when using the stricter definitions of GDPR (currently enforced in the EU) [81, 51]. While pseudonymization removes clear identifiers of persons in the data set (e.g. randomizing user IDs), anonymization deals with removing any data which might allow someone to identify (e.g. through profiling) a person from information present in the data set. Needless to say true anonymization is very rarely a trivial task. This distinction is key however, since pseudonymized data are still protected as personal data under the GDPR [81], and therefore this tool would not necessarily help in the context of sharing personal data in the EU. That being said, it might still help facilitate the private sharing of data between industry and academia or between cooperating research groups, where this distinction might not be as crucial.

2.2 Interruptibility Prediction and Biometric Sensors

The following section is based on the background provided by the original study [96]. It presents the necessary background information about using different sensors for predicting interruptibility and explains the various lag measures used to objectively quantify interruptibility.

In the past a majority of work about interruptibility prediction has been done with context-aware sensors (e.g.: [86, 38, 27, 37]). Examples of such sensors are cameras, microphones, computer interactions, pressure sensitive desk mats, etc. As the name implies, these sensors are dependent on a specific context (e.g. computer-interactions can only be tracked when working on a computer). The original study we are replicating chose to use biometric sensors instead (e.g. tracking heart rate). These sensors work independent of context and at the time when the original paper was written (2015) recent advances allowed such sensors to be small and accessible enough to be considered for

Figure 2: International 10-20 system for EEG electrode placement

future use in the field. As such, this section will focus on past efforts of using similar biometric sensors for interruptibility prediction and management.

There have been a number of related studies using biometric sensors to measure interruptibility in various situations ranging from studies done in the field to controlled laboratory environments [55, 8, 22, 21].

2.2.1 EEG

Electroencephalography (EEG) is a method to collect electrical activity caused by the brain. The way this is measured is by placing a number of electrodes on a person’s scalp. To standardize the placement of these electrodes the 10-20 system (see figure 2) was developed and presented by Jasper in 1957 [40]. EEG systems can use dry or wet electrodes, with one study indicating similar performance for both electrode types [41]. The ways how different frequencies occur in the EEG signal have previously been studied and links have been made to a number of mental states (e.g. [30, 46, 48, 33]). These frequencies can be grouped in a number of bands, namely Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta and Theta. Despite wide use there is no standardization to these frequency bands and definitions vary strongly from study to study [62].

2.2.2 Eye Tracking

Eye trackers work by shining infrared light onto the eyes of a subject and recording the reflections. By doing so, eye trackers can track eye gaze, fixations, saccades, pupil dilation and eye blinks. These features have been used in previous studies to track various mental states. For example, pupil

dilation has been used as an indicator of arousal which varies with task difficulty [13] and more recently has been integrated into an interruption management system [42].

2.2.3 ECG and BVP/PPG

Electrocardiograms (ECG) and Photoplethysmography (PPG), also referred to as Blood Volume Pulse (BVP), can all be used to measure heart activity. While ECG measures the electrical activity caused by heart muscle contractions, PPG shines light on the skin and measures how much light gets absorbed, which depends on the oxygen saturation of the blood. Apart from being used to derive heart rate features, BVP itself can be used as an indicator for cognitive load [68].

2.2.4 EDA

Electrodermal activity (EDA), also known as Skin Conductance Response (SCR) or Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), is a measurement of the electrical conductivity of the skin caused by increased activity of the sweat glands due to some stimulus and is measured via two electrodes. EDA has previously been linked to arousal, attention, stress, anxiety, emotional states and cognitive load [15, 64].

2.2.5 Body Temperature

Previous studies have found changes in body temperature as responses to stress and changes in emotions [88, 23].

2.2.6 Sensor Combination

Of course, multiple studies have combined different sensors to investigate links to psycho-physiological states [90, 34]. As an example, the authors of the original papers have combined EDA, EEG and eye tracking to assess task difficulty in a study done prior to conducting the original experiment. Furthermore, in a follow-up study they have used a combination of biometric sensors and context-aware sensors to predict interruptibility [97].

2.2.7 Interruption, Resumption and Edit Lag

The original paper mentions three most used lag measures in the literature: 1) interruption, 2) resumption and 3) edit lag. Interruption lag is the time span between being interrupted and addressing the interruption [3]. Resumption

lag is the time span between the end of dealing with the interruption and the resumption of the suspended primary task [2]. Lastly, edit lag is an extension to resumption lag measuring the time span between the end of dealing with the interruption and making the first edit action working on the suspended primary task [66].

Negotiated interruptions allow the interrupted person to decide when to address the interruption (i.e. varying interruption lag). In this context, a prior study has used interruption lag as an indicator of interruptibility [27].

3 Related Work

3.1 Replications in Empirical Software Engineering

There have been a number of systematic literature reviews and mapping studies done aiming to identify the current state of replications in empirical software engineering [24, 93, 52, 14, 4]. When combined, these studies present a comprehensive overview of studies between 1994 and 2018. In the time span of 1994 to 2012 Malaghães et al. observe a positive trend in the number of replications published in the field, growing from almost no replications to a peak of 29 replications identified in the year 2011. From 2013 onward Cruz et al. do not observe any further growth with an average of 22.8 studies per year and strong variations due to the small number of publications.

Despite their previously identified importance [76] replications remain quite scarce in the field of empirical software engineering. In the literature survey done by Zhang et al. [93] only 18 studies made up the identified 264 papers. That same survey reports that more than 90% of the identified papers are explicitly concerned about the reproducibility of their paper in one way or another (e.g. providing replication package, replication artifacts, data sources, etc.). That being said, only 23.4% of these papers provide replication packages and almost 8% do not mention concerns about replicability.

But why are there so little replications in this research field? Unsurprisingly there is no easy answer to this question, and possible factors are challenges in conducting and publishing replications, but also mixed perceptions on the role of replications [78]. In 2015, Siegmund et al. surveyed program committee and editorial board members about their views on empirical software engineering [78]. One focus point was their perceptions on replications. Surprisingly, there was a stark mismatch in which replications seemed to be appreciated by the participants, while at the same time conducting, reading or accepting replications was disliked, mainly due to the lack of novelty. However, there was no clear consensus how novel a replication

would need to be. Participants also suggested dedicated platforms to foster replications. While workshops dedicated to replication do exist (e.g. Replication in Empirical Software Engineering Research (RESER)), participants warned that workshops tend to have limited impact and that might even hinder replications because studies could be rejected from publication by arguing for a better fit in those dedicated workshops.

As previously mentioned, conducting replication studies researchers have to face unique challenges. This reportedly failed previous study [49] not only demonstrates, that these challenges should not be underestimated, but that they may also become apparent only after a large part of the experiment has already been carried out (e.g. during result analysis). In their work, Santos et al. [72] investigate these challenges by running a series of replications in the field of empirical software engineering. They identify two main challenges: 1) a lack of clarity of instructions and 2) presence of defects in provided artifacts. They also identify the following challenges reported by prior experiments:

1. New context requiring experimental design changes
2. Experimental design changes make results comparison unfeasible
3. Replication has fewer subjects than baseline
4. Participants in replication have less time than participants in the original study
5. Replication performed in a different experimental setting
6. Lack of full access to original data source
7. Unavailability of data due to change in the Version Control System

Furthermore, as a result of conducting multiple replications they identify the following set of challenges:

1. Difficulties in Setting Up the Environment
 - (a) Projects Extraction
 - (b) Dependency Problems
 - (c) Problems with Versions
2. Difficulties in Algorithm Execution
 - (a) Inconsistencies

- (b) Abnormalities in Execution
3. Difficulties in Interpreting the Paper
- (a) Lack of Familiarity
 - (b) Convergence of Results

It is important to say that the latter challenges resulted from replications of an original study without human subjects and with a replication package available. Therefore, it only serves as a subset of the potential replication challenges encountered in empirical software engineering.

3.2 Replications in Interruption Management

Going through the papers that have cited the original paper, we could not find any prior replications of the original study. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge there exist no prior replications in the research concerning interruptibility management and predicting perceived interruptibility of knowledge workers. Only when applying the very broad definition of replication proposed by Haapalainen et al. [34] we could potentially include the follow-up study [97] done by the original authors as replication, in a sense that it tries to answer the same research question building on top of the findings and methodology of the original study.

4 Original Study

The following section summarizes all relevant information about the original study we are trying to replicate. It states the research questions of the original study, summarizes the experiment design including artifacts and context variables and finally presents the originally reported results.

4.1 Original Study - Research Questions

4.1.1 Main Research Question

While the original publication does not explicitly state a research question, the author does provide one in their cumulative dissertation [94] (of which the original paper is a part of). They first ask the broader question, whether it is possible to measure the interruptibility of knowledge workers with high accuracy. They then narrow this question down for the original experiment, finally arriving at the following research question:

RQ: Can we use biometric sensors to measure interruptibility in the lab and field automatically with high accuracy?

4.1.2 Secondary Research Questions

Additionally, while never explicitly stated as research questions, the original authors mention certain findings from prior works which they are interested in confirming in addition to answering their main research question. Here is a summary of the additional observations they wanted to confirm:

- *RQ B1: Are mental load and interruptibility negatively correlated?*
- *RQ B2: Are interruptions during high mental load more disturbing?*
- *RQ B3: How do interruption, resumption and edit lag relate to interruptibility?*
- *RQ B4: What is the optimal time window duration for interruptibility prediction?*
- *RQ B5: Do participants prefer interruptions near task boundaries?*

4.2 Original Study - Participants

The original study [96] initially recruited 10 graduate students (9 male and 1 female) with majors in computer science through personal contacts. These participants had on average professional developer experience of 4.1 years ($\pm 3.8^2$) and total developer experience of 10.4 years (± 3.2). However, during data preprocessing the data of two participants could not be successfully recorded for the entire session and was therefore discarded. It is unclear to us, how this affected the distribution of gender and developer experience in the final group (e.g. gender - 7:1 vs 8:0). As compensation for their efforts, the participants were rewarded with a small chocolate gift.

4.3 Original Study - Experiment Design

The following section describes the design of the lab study reported in the original paper. The field study reported in that same paper is outside the scope of this description.

For the lab study participants had to carry out three code change tasks which are designed to represent real-world developer tasks. All participants

²Standard deviation is denoted by \pm in the following.

had to carry out the same tasks. The experiment took place in a quiet office room with external distractions and interruptions reduced to a minimum. All participants worked on the same computer using the same integrated developer environment (IDE). Each experiment was a separate one on one session.

The experiment took 90 minutes in total and was made up of three phases, 1) preparation, 2) 60-minute programming session and 3) brief follow-up interview.

Based on the original author's recollection of how the lab study was run each experiment started with greeting the participant and explaining the three code change tasks that they are tasked to carry out in the programming session. After this introductory part the preparation phase begins as described in the original study.

The preparation phase begins with a short pre-interview. After the interview the two sensor devices are placed on the participant. The experimenters then continue by recording the baseline measurement while the participants relaxes watching a fish tank movie for two minutes. Concluding the preparation, the participant was familiarized with the interruption app by doing a couple test runs while the fish tank movie continued playing in the background.

During the programming session the participants would work on three code change tasks. For this part external distractions were minimized. It was expected of the participants to work alone as much as possible, as interactions with the experimenters could affect the EEG signal. The participants were instructed to complete the task in those 60 minutes to their best efforts. It was not important that they finish all the tasks before the time ran out, in fact the design was meant to keep the participants occupied for the whole 60 minutes. After 45 minutes have passed the experimenter would ask the participant to switch to the third task, with the option to return to their current task after completing the third one. This was meant to ensure that every participant spent some time on all tasks. After 60 minutes have passed the experimenter would stop the programming session and continue with the follow-up interview.

4.3.1 Project and Tasks

The participants would work on an existing open-source project called JHot-Draw, which is a drawing framework written in Java. This project was chosen because it is a mature and well-structured open-source project with a GUI which allows participants to visually inspect the changes they would make.

Adding Circles The first task was to add a drawable circle figure. This requires adding a button to the toolbar (icon already provided) and

implementing the "draw circle" functionality. A similar function called "draw ellipse" already exists, and the participants were encouraged to reuse any existing code. The main difficulty of this task was to find the right code locations to implement the changes.

Adding Text and URL The last task required adding some unspecified text including a clickable URL to a specific dialog window. The original authors could not remember which exact dialog window this was but we assume it was the "help/about" dialog as it seemed most natural to us. The main challenge of this task was to again find the right code location for the changes but additionally to get familiar with the Java Swing GUI API.

The original authors have validated if the task difficulty varied across the tasks. To do so, they asked the participants (after the programming session) to rate each task on a scale from one to five, where one is very easy and five is very difficult. Participants rated the first and last task as rather easy (2.4 ± 0.7 and 2 ± 1.4) and the second task as rather difficult (3.9 ± 1)

4.3.2 Simulated Interruptions

While working on the programming tasks, the participants were interrupted by a tablet placed left to the workstation monitor. These interruptions would occur at random time intervals ranging from 1 to 11 minutes. This is supposed to mimic the distribution of real-life interruptions as observed in a prior study by Gonzales et al. [32]. When an interruption occurs a notification sound is played and the tablet screen turns from black to white. The participant can choose when to address the interruption, similar to how negotiated interruptions are described in prior literature [56, 27]. This also allows the experimenters to record the lag between the notification and addressing the interruption, which is called interruption lag.

Once the participant chooses to address the interruption they have to solve a two-digit multiplication exercise in their head. They then submit their answer after which the correct solution is being displayed. After that, the participant has to fill out a short survey rating disturbance, interruptibility and mental workload at the time of notification on a 5-point Likert scale. They submit the survey by pressing the "OK" button and once the screen turns black, they can resume working on the programming task.

4.3.3 Follow-Up Interview

The follow-up interview had two goals. Firstly, in order to validate the experiment design the participants were asked about their perceptions of the main programming tasks, the peripheral arithmetic task, their use of negotiated

Triggered Interruptions – negotiated

Figure 3: Illustration describing the simulated interruptions (For better readability the multiplication task and survey screen can be viewed in Figures 4 and 5)

interruptions, etc. The second part of the interview was more general, asking participants about the disruptiveness of real-world interruptions and inquiring about desired tool support that could help them manage those interruptions.

4.3.4 Data Pre-Processing

Time Windows For the interruptibility prediction model the time-dependent sensor data had to be converted into time-independent features. For each interruption a time window (ranging from 10 seconds to 3 minutes) was used with a specific duration in seconds and ending at the time of the interruption notification. The features were then calculated from the subset of data contained in each time window.

Data Cleaning and Feature Extraction: During the lab study a total of 10 hours of data were recorded from 10 participants. For two participants the biometric sensor data could not be recorded successfully for the entire session and were therefore discarded. The final data set consists of 72 samples collected from 8 participants. The interruptions were distributed quite evenly with $9 (\pm 1.6)$ interruptions per person. The sensor data were cleaned and analyzed as follows.

EEG (and Eye Blinks) The raw EEG signal was captured at 512Hz. A

Figure 4: Illustration describing the multiplication task which is part of the simulated interruptions

Figure 5: Illustration describing the survey which is part of the simulated interruptions

50Hz notch filter was applied to remove mains hum. Then using MATLAB’s pwelch function the EEG signal was split into five frequency bands: δ (0-4Hz), θ : 4-8Hz, α : (8-12Hz), β : (12- 30Hz) and γ (30-80Hz). Additionally, all possible fractions of frequency bands (e.g. α/β) as well as two ratios $\theta/(\alpha + \beta)$ and $\beta/(\alpha + \theta)$ were calculated, which according to prior findings can carry information about a person’s mental activity. The EEG headset provides two proprietary measures called ”attention” and ”meditation” sampled at 1Hz. These proprietary measures were converted into features by collecting their minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation values during the time window. Lastly, Eye Blinks were derived from the EEG signal using a peak finding algorithm as described by Manoilov [53].

Skin and Heart The raw EDA signal was split into a tonic and phasic signal using a Butterworth filter. The tonic signal was used to calculate the skin conductance level (SCL). The phasic signal was used to calculate peak related features such as number of peaks per time unit, mean of peak amplitudes, sum of peak amplitudes and area under the curve (AUC). The skin temperature was reduced to the mean and maximum temperature per time unit.

The blood volume pulse (BVP) was used to calculate the number of peaks per time unit, mean peak amplitude, heart rate and heart rate variance. Additionally, three features were calculated from the interbeat intervals (IBI); the standard deviation of the signal (SDNN), and the percentage of successive IBIs with a difference greater than 20ms (PNN20) and 50ms (PNN50).

Normalization The final pre-processing step is normalizing the data across participants. This step is important when building a general model since the biometric features are very individual and therefore hard to compare (e.g. various resting heart rates). The normalization is done by calculating each feature from the baseline recording and subtracting it from the final features. The baseline was recorded during the preparation phase where participants would watch a relaxing fish tank movie for 2 minutes.

Choosing Target Variable The original authors decided to use the subjective interruptibility ratings from the surveys as the ground truth instead of using the objective interruption lag measure. They provide two reasons for this design choice: 1) Comparability with prior work: A majority of prior work used this interruptibility measure as their ground truth. 2) Despite correlation between interruptibility and interruption lag, they are distributed differently. Ratings are distributed binomially, and interruption lags are distributed exponentially. This supports subjective observations from the experiment which found some participants addressing interruptions immediately, regardless of their interruptibility. Therefore, subjective ratings should be closer to the ground truth. This interruptibility rating is collected

via a 5-point Likert scale (1=highly interruptible / 5=not interruptible) surveys after each interruption. However, the original authors want to build models predicting 5-state and 2-state interruptibility. They derive the 2-state interruptibility by splitting the 5-point scale into 2 groups with ratings one to three being labeled "interruptible" and ratings four and five being labeled "not interruptible".

4.3.5 Building and Validating the Machine Learning Models

To build a machine learning model, the original authors had to make three choices. Firstly, which features should be used in the model. Secondly, what is the optimal time window duration for the feature extraction. Lastly, which algorithm performs best for this data set.

Feature Choice A smaller subset of features was selected for further use in the models in order to prevent overfitting. This was done using a nested correlation-based feature selection technique, namely Weka's implementation of CfsEvalSubset applied to the training sets of ten-fold cross-validation. This technique maximizes correlation between the selected features and the target variable and minimizes correlation among the selected features ³.

Algorithm Choice The original authors explain that they compared the performance of three different algorithms; 1) Naïve Bayes, 2) Decision Trees and 3) Support Vector Machines all based on Weka's implementation. In the original paper the authors do not go into detail how exactly they compared these three algorithms, only stating, that Naïve Bayes outperformed the other ones and was therefore used for the remainder of the analysis.

Time Window Choice The original authors considered different time window durations ranging from 10 seconds to 3 minutes. Although it is not explicitly stated, we assume that the authors validated each time window in the same way that the final results were obtained since in the comparison graphic (see Figure 9) the accuracies for the 10-second time window match the ones presented in the final results table (see Figure 6).

Validating the Model Performance To validate the resulting model performance, the original study used two different methods. Firstly, they use ten times ten-fold cross-validation using stratification, meaning that the class imbalance was maintained in each fold. This was done to validate how well the model performance would generalize when used on samples outside the training set but from the same participants. The original authors hope that a general model trained on a developer team would on average work good

³One thing to point out is that although CfsEvalSubset talks about correlation, it does not use typical correlation measures like Pearson R but rather uses its own set of relatedness measures.

enough for each individual member of the team. Secondly, they used leave one participant out cross-validation (which the authors call "per-participant cross-validation"). This was done to check how well the general model generalizes to new participants outside the data set. In practical terms this would mean, how well the general model would perform on a new team member in the developer team without retraining the model.

4.4 Original Study - Artifacts

The original experiment results in a number of artifacts, which are required to be able to replicate it. The following section describes all those artifacts and summarizes them in Table 2.

4.4.1 Detailed Experiment Protocol

A detailed experiment protocol is needed to keep the steps in each one-on-one session consistent. Unfortunately, the original authors do not have access to such a protocol anymore. However, a somewhat detailed guide could be derived from three sources: descriptions in the original paper, recollections of the experimenters and information from some undisclosed experiment logs. The latter two sources were supplied as an e-mail answer from the original authors. Any other gaps in the protocol had to be rebuilt from scratch (e.g. how exactly were the tasks explained to the participants).

4.4.2 Document Explaining Hexagon Geometry

The original paper mentions a "document with explanations of the geometry of a hexagon" which helps the participants to carry out the second task of the programming session. Unfortunately, the original authors did not have access to this document anymore. While replicating this study, we tried completing the three tasks beforehand. Based on this experience, we tried to replicate how this document could have looked so that it is useful to solve task two.

4.4.3 Fish Tank Movie

For the baseline measurement the participants watched a relaxing fish tank movie for two minutes. Fortunately, the original authors have provided us a YouTube link to the original video.

4.4.4 Project and Tasks: JHotDraw

A number of artifacts are required by the programming tasks (see Section 4.3.1 for a detailed explanation of the tasks, which the participants would work on). Firstly, the source code of the JHotDraw project is required. While a clean version (without the tasks being implemented) is mandatory for reproduction an optional solved version of the source code could be helpful for the replicating team to understand how the three tasks should be implemented by the participants. Additionally, the project source code requires a specific Java development kit. If possible, this should be bundled with the project code, this may not be possible however, due to licensing reasons. Lastly, the original paper mentions that for tasks one and two icons for the toolbar buttons have been provided. These icons need to be packaged with the project code.

4.4.5 Sensor Devices Used

The original experiment uses two hardware sensors: the "NeuroSky MindBand" EEG headband and the "Empatica E3" wristband sensor. Unfortunately, at the time of writing this paper both products have been discontinued and cannot be acquired through official means. That being said, for the MindBand similar devices based on the same EEG processing module are being sold and could potentially be used for replications (e.g. NeuroSky MindSet). As for the Empatica E3, the successor model E4 could be a potential alternative.

Another problem regarding the NeuroSky MindBand is the use of proprietary measures called "attention" and "meditation". While these measures can be interesting for the experimenter it is hard to replicate them when using hardware from a different manufacturer since the algorithms used for these measures are closed source.

4.4.6 Pre- and Post-Interview Questionnaires

The questionnaires used for the pre- and post-interview are necessary for the experiment. These have been provided by the original authors via e-mail.

4.4.7 Data

At the time of writing this paper, the original data could not be shared. For reproductions the raw sensor data but also the preprocessed data (e.g. cleaned, features extracted, normalized) could be interesting to double check in case some steps could not be reproduced. However, sharing the sensor data could be complicated since some data are sensitive (e.g. ECG/BVP data could

be used to identify heart health issues). Close collaborations including non-disclosure agreements could enable reproductions in these sorts of situations. Although the data themselves could not be shared, some descriptive statistics about the distribution of interruptibility ratings, could be derived from the results presented in the paper.

4.4.8 Source Code / Executable (Interruption App)

The original authors did not have access to the source code for the interruption app anymore. However, we were able to rebuild an app with the same functionality using descriptions from the original paper and from the illustrations from the conference presentation.

4.4.9 Source Code (Pre-Processing and Analysis)/ GUI Protocol (ML: Weka)

For the pre-processing of the sensor data (cleaning and feature extraction) the authors mention code written in MATLAB. This source code plus any steps involved when using other undisclosed tools would need to be documented and accessible. For the machine learning steps the original authors used the Weka framework, which is GUI based but does provide an API for integration into Java code. It is unclear to us from the original paper's description if the GUI or the Java API was used. Unfortunately, neither a step-by-step protocol (in case the original authors used the Weka GUI) nor the source code (in case they used Java code and the Weka API) could be supplied by the original authors. The protocol and source code had to be rebuilt based on the instructions in the original paper. However, even with our best efforts not all details were addressed in the paper descriptions. Especially questions about using default values, random seeds and exact implementations of certain algorithms (e.g. eye blink algorithms) are left unanswered.

4.5 Original Study - Context Variables

In the following subsection we have tried to identify as many context variables from the original experiment setup as possible. We end this section by summarizing all identified context variables in a list.

Firstly, the experiment location is important. The original study describes it as a quiet office room with external distractions and interruptions reduced to a minimum. In an optimal replication external distractions would be avoided all together, but in more realistic setups experimenters could take note of any distractions that occurred during the experiment.

Table 2: Summary of Original Study Artifacts

Artifact	Type	Access
Detailed Experiment Protocol	Document	No Direct Access
Hexagon Document	Document	No Direct Access
Fish Tank Movie	Online-Video	Online Access
JHotDraw Source Code (Clean)	Source Code	Online Access
JHotDraw Source Code (Solved)	Source Code	No Direct Access
J2SE 6 compliant JDK	Runtime	Archive Access
Task 1 & 2 Icons	Image	No Direct Access
NeuroSky MindBand	Sensor Device	Discontinued
Empatica E3	Sensor Device	Discontinued
Pre-Interview Questionnaire	Document	Supplied
Post-Interview Questionnaire	Document	Supplied
Raw Sensor Data	Data	Not Accessible
Interruption Data	Data	No Direct Access
Interruption App Source Code	Source Code	No Direct Access
Data Pre-Processing Protocol/Source Code	Document/Source Code	No Direct Access
Machine Learning Protocol/Source Code	Document/Source Code	No Direct Access

Due to the design of the experiment participants are allowed to ask questions to the experimenter during the task explanation and preparation phase. This means that the experimenters influence on each participant can vary from one session to another, depending on the answered questions.

Another variable is the presence of the experimenter during the programming session. The experimenter in the original experiment was most likely in the same room behind the participant. However, in other setups they could monitor the participant from a different room to avoid unintentional distractions.

The total experiment time can also vary. Although the programming session is a constant 60 minutes, the preparation and follow-up interview could vary in time from one session to another. This variable could also vary in replication, especially if other setups take longer or shorter to prepare.

The workstation setup also needs to be considered. In the original study a workstation with presumably one monitor is being used. The tablet for the simulated interruption is placed left to the monitor. A lot of factors can vary in workstation setup for example, keyboard, mouse, OS, OS Language, IDE Setup, Tablet etc.

The perceived difficulty of the code change tasks varies from one participant to another. This is a context variable that has been controlled in the original study. The follow-up interview surveys the participants on the perceived difficulty of the tasks.

Participants spent different amounts of time on each task. The original experiment design tries to somewhat control this variance by asking the participant to switch to task 3 for the last 15 minutes of the coding session, ensuring that each participant spends some time on each of the three tasks. That being said, although this did not happen in the original study, some participants may be able to solve all tasks faster than 60 minutes. On the other hand, some participants might spend the entire 45 minutes on the first task, which would lead to no time spent on Task 2. Both of these scenarios are not controlled by this 15-minute interruption. Therefore, time spent on each task might still vary strongly from one participant to another.

Deprecation of technology. As of writing this paper about 8 years have passed since the original paper was published. In that time the Java version used in the JHotDraw Project has been long deprecated and runtimes can only be accessed from archive mirrors. Additionally, old Java syntax might be unfamiliar to new participants, although we do not see this as a strong factor since complex Java features are not required to solve the code change tasks. The hardware used in the original experiment has also been discontinued, making stricter replication more difficult.

The number of interruptions and therefore also the time spent on in-

terruptions can vary from one participant to another. While the former is a consequence of the random timing of the interruptions, the latter comes down to the individual behavior of the participant. This variance could be reduced by employing the same pre-determined pseudo-random intervals for all participants.

The last factor we have identified is the participants' familiarity with the English language. This factor might influence many of the other context variables identified in this section. For example, preparation might take longer if the participant asks more questions due to difficulties with language comprehension. Even worse, certain explanations might not be fully understood leading to follow-up questions during the programming session, which is meant to be uninterrupted.

Summary of context variables:

1. Quiet office setting
2. Number of external distractions during experiment
3. Experimenter influence on the participant
 - (a) Questions answered during experiment
 - (a) Monitoring of the participant
4. Total experiment duration
5. Workstation setup (PC, OS, Monitor, IDE, Keyboard, Mouse, etc.)
6. Perceived difficulty of code change tasks
7. Time spent on each of the tasks / task completion
8. Deprecation of technology
9. Different amount and frequency of interruptions
10. Familiarity with the English language

4.6 Original Study - Summary of Results

Although our replication results are most comparable to the results of the lab study, we will also summarize and present the field study results as they replicate the lab study results in a more realistic context and are relevant to the comparison of results across studies in Section 9.

# States	Study	Per Instance CV			Per Participant CV			Majority Classifier
		Accuracy	Cohen's Kappa	Stdev	Accuracy	Cohen's Kappa	Stdev	Accuracy
Two	Lab	91.5%*	0.65	0.7	74.9%	-0.11	36.0	83.3%
	Field	78.6%*	0.44	1.3	69.4%	0.22	19.7	70.7%
Five	Lab	43.9%*	0.18	2.9	37.6%	0.11	21.7	38.9%
	Field	32.5%	0.13	2.1	28.2%	0.07	14.2	32.4%

Figure 6: Table 2.1 from original paper (dissertation) [97, p. 60]: Classification results by number of states and study, for per instance and per participant cross-validation (CV), compared to a majority classifier as a baseline value (* indicates that there is a significant difference in accuracy to the majority classifier).

4.6.1 Results of Interruptibility Prediction

The presented results (see Figure 6) were obtained using a 10-second time window and a Naïve Bayes classifier. The original authors only report the performances of the Naïve Bayes classifier, which reportedly outperformed⁴ the Support Vector Machine and Decision Trees classifiers. The exact method for testing and comparing classifier performance as well as the exact results of these tests are not described in the original paper and were not available to us. On the other hand, the test that lead to choosing the 10-second time window are reported by the original authors and their results are summarized in the subsequent Section 4.6.2.

The authors report the average accuracy, Cohen’s Kappa and the standard deviation of each accuracy obtained from each fold and run in the cross-validation. From the way the results are presented in the original paper, we assume that the significance was calculated via a one-sample t-test, where the majority classifier is a scalar baseline and the results of each model built in each cross-validation are the samples.

The authors interpret these results as being able to predict interruptibility with high accuracy using biometric sensors into two states (91.5%) as well as into five states (43.9%) for the ”per-instance cross-validation”. As for the ”per participant cross-validation” results, these do not yield significant improvement over the baseline accuracy, with performance varying strongly from one participant to another.

Additionally, the authors present and interpret the averaged confusion matrices obtained from the ten-times ten-fold cross-validation. Figures 7 and 8 show those confusion matrices. The authors interpret these results of the five-state confusion matrix by saying that most of the errors come from

⁴Presumably in terms of average accuracy of the models in the repeated cross-validation.

Truth	Prediction	
	interruptible	not interruptible
interruptible	58.9	1.1
not interruptible	5	7
F-Measure	0.95	0.70

Truth	Prediction	
	interruptible	not interruptible
interruptible	88.2	10.8
not interruptible	19	21
F-Measure	0.86	0.58

Figure 7: Table 2.2 from the original paper (dissertation) [96, p. 61]: Confusion matrix for Naïve Bayes classification into two states using per instance cross-validation for the lab study (left) and the field study (right) with individual class accuracies (F-measure). Green cells with bold-faced font indicate correct predictions, orange cells indicate wrong predictions. A darker background color corresponds to a larger number of data points.

Truth	Prediction				
	1	2	3	4	5
1	1.2	1.9	2.8	1.1	0
2	1.5	9.5	13.4	0.5	0.1
3	1.9	7.7	18	0.4	0
4	1	2	1.2	0.2	2.6
5	0.1	0.1	1	1.1	2.7
F-Measure	0.19	0.41	0.56	0.04	0.52

Truth	Prediction				
	1	2	3	4	5
1	2.4	12.4	2.2	1	1
2	3.2	22	6.5	2.3	11
3	2.9	12.7	5	3.1	11.3
4	1.9	4.3	6.6	5.3	6.9
5	0.1	2.3	1.7	0.5	10.4
F-Measure	0.16	0.45	0.18	0.28	0.37

Figure 8: Table 2.3 from the original paper (dissertation) [96, p. 61]: Confusion matrix for Naïve Bayes classification into five states using per instance cross-validation for the lab study (left) and the field study (right) with individual class accuracies (F-measure). Green cells with bold-faced font indicate correct predictions, orange cells indicate wrong predictions. A darker background color corresponds to a larger number of data points.

guessing adjacent classes (e.g. guessing 2 instead of 3), which they deem promising.

4.6.2 Results of Time Window Choice

Testing different time window durations (see Figure 9), they concluded that for most cases the shortest time window (10 seconds) performed the best in terms of average accuracy in repeated "per-instance" cross-validation. The only exception was the five-states classification for the field study where longer time windows performed slightly better. The authors attribute the improved performance of longer time windows in the field study to more frequent noise artifacts. In general however, the authors note that the performance did not vary very strongly across different time windows. Additionally, from the graph alone it is hard to tell if these performances were significantly different.

Figure 9: Figure 2.2 from original paper [96]: Classification accuracies for two and five categories using different time windows and Naïve Bayes

4.6.3 Results of Feature Choice

The authors present the features selected for each classification task (two-state / five-state) and each study (see Figure 10). They highlight the use of three features which were used in every single model namely, β , γ and the mean temperature. Then they discuss how not a single EDA feature was used in the field study, attributing this to increased movement noise and the short time windows. Finally, they conclude that since features from all sensors were selected (for at least two classification tasks), all sensor devices can provide value for interruptibility prediction.

4.6.4 Results of Interruption Surveys

Both studies report significant ($p < 0.0001$) and highly positive correlations ($r > 0.7$) between participants rating of disturbance, mental load and interruptibility. The authors apply Pearson's R to the results of the 5-point Likert scale surveys. They observe high positive correlations between mental load and interruptibility (Lab: $r = 0.815$; Field: $r = 0.702$) and between disruptiveness and interruptibility (Lab: $r = 0.807$; Field: $r = 0.741$). The authors interpret these high correlations as confirmation of prior findings, which argued that interruptions during high mental load moments are more

Sensor	Used Features
EEG	α [2L, 5L], α/γ [2F], α/δ [2F], β [2L, 2F, 5L, 5F], β/α [2L, 2F, 5L], β/γ [2F, 5F], β/δ [2F, 5F], β/θ [2L, 5L], γ [2L, 2F, 5L, 5F], γ/α [2L, 2F, 5L], γ/β [2F, 5F], γ/δ [2F, 5F], γ/θ [2F, 5L], δ [5L], δ/β [2L, 5L], δ/γ [2L, 2F, 5L], δ/θ [2L, 5F], θ [2L], θ/α [2L], θ/δ [2L], $\beta/(\alpha + \theta)$ [2F, 5F], Mean Attention [2F, 5F], Stdev Attention [2F], Min Meditation [2L]
Photoplethys- mograph	Mean Peak Amplitude BVP [2F], Sum Peak Amplitude BVP [2L, 5L], Max Peak Amplitude BVP [5F], Mean HR [2F], IBI PNN20 [2L, 2F], IBI NN50 [2F],
Temperature	Mean Temperature [2L, 2F, 5L, 5F]
EDA	Mean Phasic Peak Amplitude EDA [2L, 5L], Sum Phasic Peak Amplitude EDA [2L, 5L], Phasic Peak Frequency EDA [2L, 5L]

Figure 10: Table 2.4 from original paper [96, p. 2988]: Most predictive features for Naïve Bayes classification for per instance cross-validation, and their use in the classifiers (2L/2F: lab/field study two-states, 5L/5F: lab/field study five-states).

disturbing [9].

Both studies also show significant ($p < 0.001$) positive correlations between interruptibility and interruption lag (Lab: $r = 0.382$; Field: $r = 0.282$). In general, participants made use of the negotiated interruption. The average interruption lag for the lab study was 30.4 seconds (± 7.5) and 44.9 seconds (± 6.7). Furthermore, 17 out of 20 participants have used most of the interruption lags to finish the last edit. The original authors see this result as confirmation of prior work which saw participants externalize their working memory prior to addressing the interruption [27].

Lastly, the researchers report significant positive correlations between resumption and interruption lag ($r = 0.275$, $p = 0.001$) in the field study and between edit and interruption lag ($r = 0.251$, $p = 0.04$) in the lab study. In the light of these results, the authors report no strong support of the link between resumption/edit lag and interruption lag or interruptibility. No other significant ($p < 0.05$) correlations could be identified by the authors.

4.6.5 Follow-Up Interview Results

During the follow-up interview, participants were asked to rate certain situations described in previous literature. They were asked to rate those situations from 1 (strongly like) to 5 (strongly dislike). Participants preferred interruptions at the end of a task (1.5 ± 0.6) and not in the middle of a task (4 ± 0.7). They also dislike interruptions when mental workload is high (5.0 ± 0) and also when the current task is too difficult (4.4 ± 0.9). The authors report mixed results about the preference of being interrupted while being stuck or making no progress (2.5 ± 1.2) with the caveat that several participants state that they dislike interruption in those moments although recognizing the potential benefit of gaining a new perspective by taking a break in such situations.

Lastly, they asked the participants about ideas on tools that could help them with interruptions. Seven participants mentioned a tool that displays your interruptibility. Five participants mentioned tools that turn interruptions on or off depending on the mental load. Support for in-person interruptions was reported to be more urgent since these interruptions are perceived as more disruptive and cannot be ignored. However, important interruptions and interruptions which foster team spirit should not be blocked by a tool, even in high mental workload situations.

5 Experiment Design

5.1 Outline of the Replication Process

Start of Replication Process The replication process started in September 2022, at this point we have concluded an initial literature search and have decided to replicate the original study. From September, we started extracting information from the original paper. During this step, we also installed the open-source project used in the original programming tasks (JHotDraw) on our local machine, and recreated solutions to the original three tasks (see Section 4.3.1 for more details about the project and tasks).

First Interaction with the Original Experimenters After having spent some time getting familiar with the original study, we decided to contact the original authors. It took about one month and 4 emails to reach the original author, from the first email sent on October 18th, 2022, up to finally receiving answers on the 16th of November. We first tried to reach out via the original author’s academic email, which unfortunately was not active anymore, and via LinkedIn, which did not result in a response. Secondly, we sent two emails to the co-author and supervisor, who could not answer our questions, but did successfully connect us with the original author via a private email address. After we sent another reminder email to the original author on the 15th of November, we finally received two email answers on the following day. The first email confirmed the following assumptions about the experiment procedure:

1. Participants were allowed to use internet resources (e.g. Stack Overflow) during the programming sessions.
2. Participants worked on the "Draw" example inside the JHotDraw project.
3. The tasks were explained to each participant separately before each session started.
4. Participant were allowed to ask questions during the task explanation.
5. Participants were not expected to finish all tasks within the 60-minute programming session, rather participants were meant to be occupied for the whole 60 minutes.
6. Participants were not expected to take breaks during the 60-minute programming session.

The second reply provided us the following information:

1. The following materials cannot be accessed and would need to be rebuilt for the replication:
 - (a) Interruption app source code
 - (b) "Document describing hexagon geometry" used in Task 2
 - (c) Original experiment protocol
2. Based on an experiment log:
 - (a) Task 1 was completed by all ten participants
 - (b) No participant completed Task 2
 - (c) Task 3 was completed by two out of ten participants
3. Participants were asked to move on to Task 3 after about 45 minutes have passed to ensure that each participant spends some time on each of the tasks
4. Participants were instructed to work "best effort" and that they were explicitly not expected to finish all tasks in time
5. Interactions with the participants during the programming session were reduced to a minimum to avoid artifacts in the EEG signal
6. The following materials were supplied:
 - (a) Slide deck of the conference presentation with additional information and screenshots of the interruption app to help in rebuilding
 - (b) Link to "the fish tank movie" used for the baseline recording
 - (c) Pre- and Post-Interview questionnaires

Rebuilding Lab Setup While contacting the original authors (November 2022), we also inquired about access to our university's lab, gaining access in January 2023, as was planned. In the time between November 2022 and January 2023 we rebuilt the interruption app and the experiment protocol. After gaining access to the lab and to our sensor devices, we started recreating the experiment setup in the lab, arriving at a working setup by March 2023.

Test Run On March 10th, 2023, we practiced the experiment procedure by doing a test run with a colleague. This test run was meant to simply go through all experiment session steps (e.g. task explanation, electrode placement, starting recording, interviews, etc.). The test participant was not a developer, therefore, they were instructed to transcribe random text (i.e. "lorem ipsum") into a text editor, instead of performing the code change task.

Second Interaction with the Original Experimenters Gaps identified in the experiment protocol prompted a second round of interactions with the original author. On March 13th, 2023, we contacted them and received a reply on the same day. The following questions were answered:

- **Q:** How were unexpected issues which occur during the programming session handled?
- **A:** If possible, the experimenter would solve the issue and continue with the experiment. The experimenter would log when the issue occurred and later check if the issue influenced the collected data.
- **Q:** How were the Pre-/Post-Interviews recorded?
- **A:** Given the participant's consent, the interviews were recorded using an audio recorder.
- **Q:** Did the participant track the time during the experiment, or was this done by the experimenter? If so, did the participant have a special timer for this purpose.
- **A:** The experimenter started and stopped the experiment. The participant did not need to track time. The participant only had access to the time shown on the workstation PC.

Pilot Session On March 14th we conducted a pilot run to test the experiment procedure a final time before conducting the experiment sessions. The study supervisor would monitor the pilot as an observer and note any feedback which needed to be addressed. The pilot run was performed without any major issues. The following feedback was collected during the pilot:

1. The presenter may present in a friendly but efficient manner, avoiding unnecessary interactions (jokes, tangents), where possible
2. If questions from participants during the preparation phase are allowed, this should be consistent for all sessions

3. Pre-Interview question on "biological sex" should be revised to "gender identity"
4. The participant should be explicitly instructed that the mental arithmetic task should be solved without using any tools (i.e. in their head)
5. The instruction to "avoid closing windows" might be removed since it is redundant after employing the "Hide Windows Tool"

All of these points were incorporated into the final version of the experiment protocol.

Finding Participants Finding participants took place between February and May 2023. During February and March, we drafted participants from our personal and professional contacts, while also announcing our experiment on the talent pool website [REDACTED]. A first draft of the participant selection was created on March 10th, including two reserve participants in case of others dropping out. Luckily, we were able to recruit one additional participant through one of the participants. In the end, the first round of finding participants resulted in finding 8 out of the 10 final participants.

Due to three potential participants cancelling in April, as well as the two reserve participants not being able to participate, a second round of finding participants was started. We found three potential participants, out of which one took part in the experiment and the two others either cancelled or did not respond. We were able to recruit the final participant in a third round of finding participants in May 2023.

Experiment Sessions Carrying out the experiment sessions took place over a timespan of 3 months, with 7 out of 10 sessions taking place between late March and early April 2023 and the 3 remaining sessions taking place between mid of April and late May due to problems with finding participants.

Data Analysis Data analysis started in April 2023 after 8 out of the 10 experiment sessions were held and took about 3 months until July 2023.

Final Interaction with the Original Experimenters Before starting data analysis in April 2023, we tried to contact the original author if they could share the original source code. After 3 weeks, we sent a reminder, but ultimately received no answer. At the time of writing this study (August 2023), we have compiled a list of open questions for the original authors and have sent out another email and are currently awaiting an answer.

Table 3: Overview Table of the Replication Procedure

	Test Sessions	Pilot Sessions	Experiment Sessions
#Sessions	1	1	10
Time Frame	March 10th 2023	March 14th 2023	March-May 2023
#Participants	1	1	10
Duration in Hours	2	2	20
Total Duration of Experiment Data	NA	1h5m34s	10h34m14s
Total Duration of Recorded Baseline Data	NA	2m40s	25m34s
#Interruption Samples	NA	10	82
#EEG Samples	NA	1,048,064	10,134,528
#ECG Samples	NA	1,048,064	10,134,528
#EDA Samples	NA	131,008	1,266,816
#Temp. Samples	NA	131,008	1,266,816

5.2 Experiment Design incl. Deviations from Original Study

We have tried replicating the original experiment as closely as possible. Due to initially planning on doing an extension and replication (adding eye tracking and computer interaction monitoring), certain steps vary from the original to accommodate the use of extra sensors. We have taken note of any intentional or unintentional deviations from the original experiment. For a better overview, each subsection will be followed by a table summarizing the deviations presented in the corresponding subsection (See Tables 4,6,7,8,9,11,12).

5.2.1 Summary of Deviations

In total, we identify 50 deviations from the original experiment.

Out of those deviations 43 deviations were intentional (e.g. adapting the design to the new context) and 7 were unintentional (e.g. configuration error). Out of the intentional deviations 31 could have been avoided (e.g. by leaving out the extension) and 12 were unavoidable (e.g. lack of clarity of instructions). Out of the 7 unintentional deviations, 6 were avoidable (e.g. configuration errors) and a single deviation was unavoidable (e.g. D33:

defects in the original artifacts).

Santos et al. identify the challenge of "new context requiring design changes" in prior replication literature [72]. We have identified 18 deviations which match this description. Out of these 18 deviations, 7 were a result of the extension (e.g. D24: single-monitor setup due to eye tracker limitations).

In their work Santos et al. discover two main challenges based on the observations they made during multiple replications [72]. These are 1) lack of clarity of the instructions and 2) presence of defects in the provided artifacts. Observing the former, 7 deviations were caused by a lack of clarity in instructions (mostly due to the lack of access to source code). On the other hand, the latter, was the cause of only a single deviation, namely the wrong questionnaire being supplied.

5.2.2 Finding Participants

Channels Used for Finding Participants For our study, we tried replicating the original participant profile as closely as possible. We have recruited 6 participants via personal contacts (colleagues, friends) and 4 participants by advertising the experiment on a talent pool website [REDACTED] designed to connect industry with university students. In order to save time, finding participants and carrying out the experiments was done in parallel. In contrast, the original authors have recruited all participants via personal contacts (i.e. convenience sampling) (D1).

Finding participants with an exact replication profile proved to be quite challenging and despite our best efforts certain deviations could not be avoided.

Number of Participants - Experiment In total we have recruited 10 participants for our replication of the lab study. The original study recruits 10 participants for the lab study and another 10 participants for the field study. However, for the original lab study the data of 2 participants could not be recorded correctly. Therefore, the final number of participants used for the models in the original lab study is 8. We have decided to carry out the experiment with 10 participants replicating the original goal of the lab study instead of replicating a smaller number of participants caused by an error (D2).

Number of Participants - Interview Analyzing the post-interview questionnaires, the original study pools together the answers from both lab and field study resulting in 20 participants. In comparison, we only interviewed 10 participants since we only replicated the lab study (D3).

Academic Profile We managed to find 4 graduate students but also had 2 undergrad students, 3 full time developers (2 master graduates and 1 bachelor graduate), and 1 ■■■ graduate (■■■■ Technical upper-level secondary school). Although academic progress varied significantly, we made sure that each participant at least majored in computer science (or in the case of the ■■■ graduate were preparing to major in computer science). This deviates from the original study, which recruited 10 graduate students with computer science majors (D4).

Gender Distribution Our final selection consisted of 8 male and 2 female participants. The original distribution of genders was 9 male and 1 female participant (or 7 male and 1 female since the data of two participants were dropped in the original experiment) (D5).

Developing Experience Our participant have an average total developing experience of 5.5 Years \pm 2.6 an average professional developing experience of 3.3 Years \pm 3.1. Although having tried to control for this factor, compared to the original study, we have a significantly lower average total experience than the 10.4 Years \pm 3.2 (D6) and a slightly lower professional developing experience than the 4.1 Years \pm 3.8 (D7). We presume that in the study the participants started coding well before attending university, whereas in our mix most participants seem to have started coding at the same time as attending university.

Compensation Moving on from participant profile, the participants were compensated by receiving €20 for a total time commitment of 2 hours (this includes a time buffer). In comparison, in the original study, the participants received a chocolate gift(D8). Nevertheless, we chose to adhere to the standard hourly rate usually used for our university lab’s subject pool■■■.

5.2.3 Recreating Sensor Devices Setup

Sensor Device Choice To replicate the original experiment we needed a device capable of capturing the following 4 measures: 1) single channel EEG, 2) BVP, 3) EDA and 4) skin temperature. For this purpose, we chose the NeXus-10 MKII by MindMedia⁵. It is a lab-grade multi-sensor device using high-quality sensors with very low noise signal (including shielded cables for the sensor connections) and the ability to record data at very high sampling frequencies (up to 8192 Hz for EEG and ECG inputs). Doing a replication,

⁵<https://www.mindmedia.com/en/products/nexus-10-mkii/>

Table 4: Summary table of all deviations from the original participant profile

ID	Deviation	Original	Replication
D1	Source of Participants	Personal Contacts	Mix of: Personal Contacts (6) and Talent Pool Advertisement (4)
D2	Number of Participants - Experiment	Lab: 8-10; Field: 10	10
D3	Number of Participants - Interview	Pooled together Lab and Field: 20 (10+10)	10
D4	Academic Profile	10 Graduate Students (Major in Computer Science)	4 Graduate Students (Major in Computer Science) + 3 Full Time Developers (1 Bachelor/2Masters) + 1 █████ Graduate
D5	Gender Mix	9 male, 1 female	8 male, 2 female
D6	Total Developing Experience	10.4 Years \pm 3.2	5.5 Years \pm 2.6
D7	Professional Developing Experience	4.1 Years \pm 3.8	3.3 Years \pm 3.1
D8	Compensation	Small Chocolate Gift	€20

protrusion of bone just behind the ear). As for the reference electrode, in the original study, it was placed on the left ear lobe (**D13**). We have tried using an ear clip for the reference electrode, but could not get a reliable connection. Therefore, we tried using an electrode pad on the left mastoid instead, which worked more reliably. This alternative reference placement is also recommended by the manufacturer of the NeuroSky MindBand used in the original study [61]. Since the thick mastoid bone should block out most brain waves from reaching the electrode, it should provide functionally the same reference as an electrode placed on the ear lobe. We recognize that EEG reference electrode placement is not a straightforward task and the benefits and drawbacks of this setup are discussed in much more detail in other EEG literature [91]. However, due to the goals and scope of this reproduction, we wanted to find a reference method equivalent to the original method rather than trying to improve on the original study design.

Ground Electrode Placement The ground electrode was placed on the left collar bone, as grounding was shared with the ECG setup. This deviates from the original experiment, where the ground electrode was placed at the left ear (**D15**).

ECG: Electrode Placement For the ECG recording, we used the same type of electrode pads as for the EEG sensor. The positive electrode was placed on one of the bones at the lower left rib cage, the negative electrode was placed on the right collar bone. This electrode placement was based on the recommendation from the Nexus-10 MKII software. This setup was reliable in our tests and heart beats were easily identifiable when visually inspecting the ECG signal.

Sensor Sampling Rate For this replication, we set the EEG sampling rate at 256 Hz. This was the consequence of a misconfiguration of our EEG setup. Although the Nexus-10 MKII is capable of recording up to 8192 samples per second, the default configuration for EEG is set at 256 Hz. Therefore, our sampling rate is half as fast as the original 512hz (**D15**). ECG (substituting BVP) was also sampled at 256 Hz, while EDA and Temperature were sampled at 32 Hz. This is much faster than the 4 Hz used in the original study for BVP, EDA and Temperature (**D16**). For a discussion on how the differing sample rate might affect the comparability of results, see Section 6.

EDA: Dry vs Wet Electrodes For recording EDA, we used the same wet electrodes, which we used for ECG and EEG. The dry electrodes included in

Table 5: Overview of Sensor Types

	Original	Replication
Brain-Related Features	1-Channel EEG (512 Hz), Dry Electrode (+: FP1; -: Left Earlobe)	1-Channel EEG (256 Hz), Wet Electrode (+: FP1; -: Left Mastoid)
Heart-Related Features	BVP-Sensor (4 Hz) (Left Wrist)	ECG (256 Hz) (+: Lower Left Rib Cage; -: Right Collar Bone)
Skin Conductivity Response	Dry Electrode (4 Hz) (Left Wrist)	Wet Electrode (32 Hz) (Left Wrist)
Temperature	Simple Sensor (4 Hz) (Left Wrist)	Cable Simple Sensor (32 Hz) (Right Wrist)
Grounding	EEG: Left Earlobe	Common Grounding: Left Collar Bone
	Heart/Skin/Temperature: Left Wrist	

our setup were finger mounted, which was not suitable for the programming tasks, which involve a lot of finger movement. This is why we used electrode pads on the left wrist. In contrast, the original study used dry electrodes in the Empatica E3 wristband (**D18**).

EDA: Wrong Electrodes While in general, use of wet electrodes for EDA is not a problem, the type of gel we used was not suited for this task. For EDA, an isotonic electrolyte gel is needed which has the same salt concentration as the excreted sweat. Our pads had far higher salt concentration, which lead to the problem where eccrine glands can become saturated, resulting in no sweat response in the measured location [59]. This resulted in a measurement error, which was only discovered after the experiment sessions were concluded. Unfortunately, the EDA signal of the majority of sessions was unusable, which is why we had to discard all EDA features for our replication (**D19**).

Temperature: Sensor Placement Lastly, the temperature sensor had to be moved to the right wrist, due to the EDA sensors electrodes taking up too much space on the left wrist, deviating from the original measurement location which was the left wrist (**D20**).

Table 6: Summary table of all deviations from the original sensor setup

ID	Deviation	Original	Replication
D9	Hardware	NeuroSky MindBand + Empatica E3	NeXus-10 MKII by MindMedia
D10	Sensor Wires	Wireless	8 Wires Between Participant and Sensor Device
D11	Sensor Type	BVP	ECG
D12	EEG Electrode Type	Dry Electrode	Wet Electrode (Adhesive Gel Pads)
D13	EEG Reference Electrode Placement	Ear Clip	Mastoid Behind Left Ear
D14	EEG Ground Electrode Placement	Ear Clip	Left Collar Bone
D15	EEG Sampling Rate	512 Hz	256 Hz
D16	ECG/BVP Sampling Rate	4 Hz	256 Hz
D17	EDA & Temperature Sampling Rate	4 Hz	32 Hz
D18	EDA Electrode Type	Dry Electrode	Wet Electrode (Adhesive Gel Pads) (Non-Isotonic → Wrong Electrode Type!)
D19	EDA Signal	Used	Discarded
D20	Temperature Sensor Placement	Left Wrist	Right Wrist

5.2.4 Recreating the Experiment Context

Quiet Office Space We have conducted our experiment in lab D here at the [REDACTED]. This lab is a small room with one large conference table placed near the entrance and two other tables placed against the opposite wall. It has window blinds which completely block out outside light, therefore, eliminating changes in natural lighting. We tried replicating the original study’s description of a quiet office space with minimal external distraction.

Experimenter Presence The room also features a one-way mirror. This enabled us to monitor the participant from another room, leaving the participant to work alone during the programming task. As a consequence, the participants were instructed to raise their hand if experimenter help would be required. Based on the authors not mentioning any sort of monitoring setup, we assume that they were sitting behind the participant in the same room during the programming session. Therefore, our setup deviates from the original in the way we monitored the participant (**D21**). The rationale for this change was to further minimize the experimenters influence on the participant during the programming session.

Special Chair and Posture In our setup, the participant would sit in a special office chair without wheels and with an adjustable head rest. The participants were instructed to place their heads against the head rest and keep it there for the whole duration of the programming session, except when dealing with the interruptions on the tablet. The participants were also instructed to look at the main monitor at all times, except when dealing with the interruptions. All of this was done so that the eye tracker, used in the initially planned extension, would work correctly. The type of sensor used needed the participant to keep their head relatively still in one position, and only worked while the participant was looking at the screen. The original study uses a regular office chair with no special instructions on posture, which we deviate from with a more restrictive setup (**D22**).

Single- vs. Multi-Monitor In our replication, we have used a single monitor setup with the tablet placed left of the monitor. Due to the restrictions of the eye tracker we used, we could not use multiple monitors. The original study most likely uses a multi-monitor setup, as depicted in the photo from the original paper (see Figure 12). The photo depicts a multi-monitor setup with the tablet being placed left to the main monitor. Although we do not know how many monitors were used in the lab study, we thought that the

authors might try to keep the setup somewhat similar to the field study. Therefore, our setup most likely deviates in using a single monitor rather than multiple ones (D24).

Workstation: OS and IDE Our workstation PC is running on Windows 10 and use IntelliJ as the IDE. Judging from the photo presented in the original paper (see Figure 12), the original study also uses some older Windows release (D25). The IDE used in the original experiment is Eclipse. Due to the extension, we used a different IDE since the IDE interactions tracker we wanted to use was only available for IntelliJ and not for Eclipse (D26).

JHotDraw Project The participants had to work on three code change tasks in the JHotDraw project. Although not explicitly stated, we assume that the authors meant specifically the "draw" example contained in this project, given it fits the description of the project most closely. To use the exact version of this project, we had to install an exact Java development kit version (J2SE 6 compliant). This version has been unsupported for so long that, when we installed the newest IntelliJ IDE version in the lab, it did not support this Java version anymore, and we had to roll back to a prior release. The exact IntelliJ release (as well as all artifact versions) used will be documented in the replication package (see Section 5.3).

Task Difficulty For the original study, the authors wanted the perceived difficulty to vary between the tasks. In order to compare this factor and spot any potential deviation from the original experiment, we have replicated this validation step. In the follow-up interview, participants were asked to rate their perceived difficulty of each task on a scale from one (= "very easy") to five (= "very difficult"). Perceived difficulty of tasks one and three (3 ± 1.3 and 2.6 ± 1.4) were on average slightly higher than in the original experiment (2.4 ± 0.7 and 2 ± 1.4), but not by a significant amount. Meanwhile, task two has been perceived almost exactly the same as in the original (3.9 ± 1.4 vs. 3.9 ± 1). In conclusion, our results have shown no significant difference in perceived task difficulty between the original and replication experiments (D27).

Task Completion Another similar factor is task completion. In our replication, four participants completed task one, only one participant completed task two and finally task three was completed by two participants. Based on information from the first round of e-mails, we know that in the original lab study all participants managed to finish the first task, none could finish

Figure 11: Replicated Study Setup - Sensors placed on the participant are denoted by letters: (A): EEG electrodes placed at FP1 (+) and at left mastoid (-); (B) ECG electrodes placed at right collarbone (-) and lower left side of rib cage (+); (C): Two EDA electrodes placed on left wrist; (D): Ground electrode placed on left collarbone; (E): Temperature sensor placed on right wrist;

Figure 12: Figure 1 from Original Paper [96, p. 2984]: "Study setup for one participant wearing the headband and wristband in the field study. The tablet for triggering interruptions is placed next (left) to the participant's main screen."

the second task and two out of the ten participants managed to finish the third task. Compared to the original experiment, task one had a far lower completion rate, while tasks two and three had a similar completion rate (D28).

Task Completion II: Reasons for Not Finishing When asking why participants could not finish the tasks, most of them mentioned having not enough time. This is the same reason given by the participants in the original study. However, the participants which could not finish the first task in time provided a second reason, namely, problems navigating the project. We speculate that this could have been caused by the task explanation not being detailed enough, but it could have also been caused by different factors such as the deviations in participant profile (e.g. lower total development experience) or even just by other factors.

Task Completion III: The Outlier The one participant that solved the second task was a bit of an outlier since they managed to solve all three tasks in about 25 minutes. They continued working on the project for the remaining 35 minutes, implementing other possible changes they could think

of. We recognize that the procedure for this one participant deviates from the original, where no participant finished all tasks (**D29**). We have inspected how this affected the perceived interruptibility of this participant. We see that the participant remained highly interruptible for four interruptions after being finished with the original tasks, but returned to being less interruptible for the last two interruptions, where they most likely were focused on a new task they came up with. Given that the participant’s behavior still fulfilled the original goal of the experiment design, which is being focused working on a development task, we ultimately decided not to discard these data points.

5.2.5 Recreating the Experiment Protocol

Experiment Procedure Since the original experiment protocol could not be retrieved, we had to rebuild from the somewhat detailed description of the steps, which the original author described based on their recollection of the experiments. Based on this description, an extra step was added to the experiment procedure, which was completely omitted from the original paper. The experimenter would inform the participant to switch to task 3 after about three thirds of the experiment having passed. This was done to ensure a somewhat even distribution of time spent on each task.

Task Explanation, Interruptions and Other Instructions For the replication, we have decided to use a PowerPoint presentation for these explanations. All other instructions were also explicitly written down in the protocol and read to the participant, again to minimize variance. We assume the tasks and the simulated interruptions were originally explained verbally in a non-structured manner. We have deviated from this unstructured approach to minimize variance between one session and another (**D30**).

Preparation Time Due to the use of different sensor devices (see Section 5.2.3) the preparation procedure took longer than in the original, taking approximately 30 to 45 minutes rather than the 15 minutes preparation of the original study (**D31**). That being said, the original study does not seem to include the task explanation in the preparation time, therefore it is hard to exactly compare how much time preparation took.

Tracking Time and Logging Events To record time during the experiment, we used a simple stopwatch app. As a precaution, as an observer, we made additional notes when each interruption occurred and noted unplanned events which could impact the experiment.

Table 7: Summary table of all deviations from the original experiment context

ID	Deviation	Original	Replication
D21	Monitoring Participant	In the same room	In an adjacent room through one-way mirror
D22	Participant Sitting/Posture Arrangement	Simple Office Chair / No Instructions	Special Chair without Wheels and with Adjustable Headrest / Instructed to keep Head placed against Headrest at all times except when dealing with interruptions
D23	Participant Gaze Instructions	No Instructions	Instructed to look at the Monitor at all times during programming session (except when dealing with interruptions)
D24	Monitor Setup	Unknown / Multi-Monitor	Single Monitor Setup
D25	Workstation OS	Windows Vista/7/8?	Windows 10
D26	IDE Choice	Eclipse	IntelliJ
D27	Perceived Difficulty (1 = "very easy"; 5 = "very difficult")	Task 1 (2.4 ± 0.7); Task 2 (3.9 ± 1); Task 3 (2 ± 1.4)	Task 1 (3 ± 1.3); Task 2 (3.9 ± 1.4); Task 3 (2.6 ± 1.4)
D28	Task Completion	Task 1: 10/10; Task 2: 2/10; Task 3: 0/10	Task 1: 4/10; Task 2: 1/10; Task 3: 2/10
D29	Task Completion General	No participant managed to end before the 60 minutes have passed.	One participant managed to finish all tasks after about 25 minutes. Came up and implemented additional tasks in the remaining 35 minutes.

Experimenter Interventions during Interruptions In the event where the programming session would end during an interruption, we would wait until that last interruption was completed before interfering. We applied the same rule, when reminding the participants to move on to task three after 45 minutes passed.

Interview Questionnaires Both pre-interview and post-interview were very similar to the original experiment, given that we had access to the original questionnaires. Both interviews were recorded using an audio recording device, which is also how the interviews were originally recorded.

Skipping Interview Questions Since we searched for participants with a specific profile, questions about developer experience were skipped during the pre-interview since they were already answered before the experiment via email (D32).

Wrong Questions Supplied The supplied post-interview questionnaire ended with a set of open questions, which is how they were asked in the replication. One of those questions was phrased as such: "When does the interruption bother you most, when not?". After rereading the original study, we noticed that this question seems to have been rephrased as a set of closed questions at some point since the original paper omits this question and instead reports answers a set of closed questions (D33). These closed questions ask the participant to rate certain situations on a scale from 1 ("strongly like") to 5 ("strongly dislike"). All of these situations described some moment of interruption and were identified in previous literature by the original authors. Unfortunately, we noticed this difference only after the experiment sessions took place.

Extension-Specific Steps The extension led to two extra steps in the replicated protocol. Firstly, the eye tracker required a calibration step where participants had to be correctly positioned in front of the tracker and follow some calibration points with their gaze (D34). Secondly, we recorded an additional baseline, where the participant would look at a black on white fixation cross for two minutes (D35). This was done to measure the baseline pupil size.

Starting and Stopping Sensor Recording For the replication, we started and stopped the recording three times (once for each of the two baseline measurements and once for the programming session). When going through

Table 8: Summary of all deviations from the original experiment procedure

ID	Deviation	Original	Replication
D30	Task Explanation	Informal verbal explanation	PowerPoint Presentation
D31	Preparation Time	15 Minutes	30–40 Minutes
D32	Pre-Interview Questions	Including Developing Experience Questions	Skipping Developing Experience Questions (answered beforehand)
D33	Post-Interview Questions	Favorable Interruption Contexts Survey as Closed Questions	Favorable Interruption Contexts Survey as Open Questions
D34	Additional Steps	-	Eye Tracker Calibration
D35	Additional Steps	-	Eye Tracker Baseline Recording
D36	Recording Procedure	Starting and Stopping Recording Once; Using separate timestamps to delimit different phases (e.g. baseline recording, programming session)	Starting and Stopping Recording three times (baseline, baseline eye tracker, programming session)
D37	Monitoring Participant Activity	Screen Capture Recording	No Screen Capture Recording; Mouse + Keyboard and IDE Activity Tracking

the e-mails with the authors a second time, we noticed that they most likely started and stopped the recording only once, keeping track of the different phases via separately recorded timestamps (**D36**). This deviation originates from a misunderstanding of the original description of the preparation phase.

Screen Recording For the replication, we did not use a screen recorder. Although this deviates from the original design, this decision was made under the assumption that screen recording might be redundant due to already tracking IDE interactions, computer interaction, and window activity as part of the extension (**D37**). However, this assumption would be incorrect as discussed in more detail in Section 6.

5.2.6 Recreating the Interruption App

Since the original authors did not have access anymore to the interruption app source code, we had to rebuild it, based on the description from the original paper plus some concept designs featured in the conference presentation which the authors send us via e-mail. We rebuilt the app in Electron; a cross-platform JavaScript framework built with Node.js and Chromium. The interruption data were saved as a CSV file locally on the tablet. The source to this app will be open-source and available in the replication package. We are quite confident that our interruption app is functionally identical to the original app, only potentially varying in design (e.g. font style and size, layout) and in the chosen notification sound (**D38**). Additionally, two changes were made to the original design: 1) a demo mode and 2) a head rest reminder screen.

Demo Mode In the preparation phase, the experimenter guides the participant through a number of simulated interruptions to familiarize the participant with how they function. To optimize this process, we created a demo mode, which displays interruptions exactly every 10 seconds. We assume that this deviates from the original procedure, where presumably there was no special mode for demoing the simulated interruptions (**D39**). This demo mode serves three purposes. Firstly, we save some time, not having to wait for the random time intervals between 1 and 11 minutes each. Secondly, the demo runs are more consistent across participant since we remove the element of randomness by using constant time intervals. Thirdly, the demo mode does not output data to avoid confusion after the data collection. The experimenter can enable this mode in the start screen.

Head Rest Reminder Screen Due to the planned extension of using eye trackers, the participants had to keep their head placed against a head rest for the whole duration of the programming session. During our pilot experiment, we noticed that at some point the participant forgot to maintain this posture. Therefore, we implemented one extra information screen, reminding the participant to keep their head placed against the head rest. The participants had to confirm this information by pressing a button on the screen during each interruption before continuing to work. Needless to say, this extra screen deviates from the original app design (**D40**). The experimenter can disable this feature in the start screen.

Interruption Frequency Due to the interruption app design, interruption frequency will vary based on the random timing, but also on how much time a

Table 9: Summary of all deviations from the original interruption app design

ID	Deviation	Original	Replication
D38	Interruption App Design	Unknown	Potentially: Different Fonts, Layout and Notification Sound
D39	Interruption App Design	No Demo Mode	Displaying Interruption every 10 seconds
D40	Interruption App Design	-	Additional information screen reminding participant to keep head placed against head rest
D41	Interruption Frequency	9(\pm 1.6) Interruptions per Participant	8.2(\pm 1) Interruptions per Participant (not significantly lower)

Figure 13: Activity Diagram of the Data Processing Steps

participant spends on each interruption. Although we had on average slightly fewer interruptions per participant (8.2 ± 1) than the original study (9 ± 1.6), this difference is not significant ($p = 0.24$)⁷ (**D41**). We conclude that the slightly lower interruption frequency is most likely a result of the randomness in the experiment design.

5.2.7 Recreating the Data Processing

In this section we go over the various data processing steps we needed to replicate. Figure 13 provides an overview of all these data processing steps.

⁷To derive statistical significance we performed a Welch’s t-test.

Parsing and Syncing Data Due to the different devices used, the data first need to be reformatted from the NeXus-10 MKII export format. Although it exports the data in CSV, the first couple of lines include metadata such as participant name and start time of the recording. Additionally, rather than using timestamps, the export format uses a simple integer index counting up from 0 for each sample point. To sync the data with the interruption data set, we convert those index values to timestamps using the recording start timestamp from the metadata as a reference. The timestamp provided in the metadata has a precision of one second, we understand that using this timestamp for syncing means that the interruption timestamp may be off by at most 1 second (rushing or lagging). A more precise way could have been to use the event trigger system of the NeXus-10 MKII so that each interruption notification is recorded in the sensor as a trigger event. That being said, since the original paper uses three different sources of time (two sensors and the tablet for the interruption app) and no special synchronization steps are described, we assume that the syncing of interruption data and sensor data was done with the same precision as our replication.

Calculating Two State Interruptibility After this step, we calculate the two-state interruptibility ratings in the interruption data set from the five-state ratings as described in the original study [96], where ratings one to three are labeled as "interruptible" and rating four and five are labelled "not interruptible".

Python vs. MATLAB In the original study, the authors use MATLAB for the EEG signal processing. Furthermore, although not explicitly stated, we assume that MATLAB was also used for the signal processing of the other sensor data (i.e. ECG/BVP, EDA, temperature). Where possible, we wanted to provide artifacts in the replication packages which do not require proprietary technology, therefore, we chose to use Python instead of MATLAB (**D42**). Although this deviates from the original experiment, the Python library SciPy includes ports of MATLAB's signal functions, which includes the `pwelch` function and the Butterworth filters used in the original paper. However, there is one important difference between the two implementations, namely their default values. Since the original paper does not specify the window length used for the `pwelch` function, we assume that they use the defaults. As discussed in this thread⁸, the default behavior of SciPy's `pwelch` implementation is to set each segment to 256 samples, while MATLAB's implementation divides the data into 8 equally sized segments.

⁸<https://dsp.stackexchange.com/questions/84193>

We have written our code in such a way that this default behavior is correctly replicated.

EEG Signal Cleaning Before we proceed with sampling the data into the different time windows, we apply some data filtering on the entire data set. Firstly, inspecting the technical specification [60] of the "TGAM" EEG module used in the NeuroSky MindBand, we discovered that it outputs RAW data with a frequency range of 3-100 Hz. We speculate that the low end is missing to avoid low frequency drift and movement noise, which could be more prevalent with dry electrode setups due to the electrodes' high impedance. However, this would mean that only the upper 1/4 of the δ bands (0-4 Hz) frequency content is actually present in the original data. In order to emulate this characteristic, we applied a fifth order Butterworth filter (bandpass: 3-100 Hz). This characteristic could explain why the original authors did not specify a processing step for filtering out noise from movement and low frequency drift. We then apply the 50 Hz notch filter (second order Butterworth filter - bandpass 49-50 Hz) to remove some of the noise resulting from mains hum.

EEG Signal Filtering: Eye Blink Detection For the eye blink extraction, we also filter on the entire data set. Unfortunately, in the original paper, the description of the eye blink detection algorithm is very vague only specifying the use of a Butterworth filter in combination with a peak finding algorithm and then pointing to a methodology in a paper by Manoilov [53]. Inspecting the paper ourselves, we find two possible implementations for automatic eye blink detection. The first one works by setting a simple amplitude threshold, while the second inspects the power spectra of the frequency band of 2-3Hz. We have tried to conceptually replicate this approach by filtering out the mid to high frequency content and applying a peak detection algorithm to the signal. We are not sure how reliable this method is, but the resulting features at least seemed to match up with the slightly lower average eye blinking frequency of a person that is reading (a state which we assumed to be similar to programming). However, it is unclear if the original authors, performed additional cleaning steps (especially cleaning the previously detected eye movement, which is considered as noise in the EEG signal). As such our eye blink detection might deviate from the original implementation (**D43**). At the time of writing, we asked for clarification from the original authors. However, for the replication, we assumed, that no further data cleaning was done by the authors.

Sampling Interruption Time Windows Now we split the (filtered) data into the smaller samples for each interruption and time window duration. The following steps are performed inside a loop for each of the generated samples.

Calculating Brain-Related Features and Eye-Blink Extraction As described in the original paper, we calculate each frequency band’s band-power using the pwelch function. We then compute all possible fractions of bandpowers (e.g. α/β , α/γ , etc.) and two specific fractions described in the original paper ($\theta/(\alpha + \beta)$ and $\beta/(\alpha + \theta)$) [96]. For the eye blink extraction, we use a peak-detection algorithm on the EEG signal filtered specifically for eye blink detection.

Calculating Heart-Related Features For the ECG data, we use the NeuroKit2 library, which has processing pipelines for both ECG and BVP data. The original paper does not specify the exact algorithms used to derive the various heart related features. Therefore, we could only implement code which produces the same expected output. As such, the exact processing of heart related features might have deviated from the original methods (D44).

Cleaning EDA Signal As described in the Section 5.2.3, we had to discard the EDA data due to a setup error. Nevertheless, the data of one session did not seem to be impacted strongly by the error, and we have recreated the EDA processing code for this one example. This was only done as reference for future replications and was not used in any consequent machine learning steps. The implementation of the EDA signal processing is based on the descriptions in the original paper and might deviate from the original implementation (D45). The original paper first filters out noise in the EDA data by applying an exponential filter. The exact alpha value used for the filtering was not specified. In another paper, an alpha value of 0.8 was used [36]. However, in our data only values smaller than 0.2 resulted in visible smoothing. The Neurokit2 Library uses a fourth order Butterworth low pass filter with a 3 Hz cutoff instead for cleaning. However, it is unclear whether this filtering is really necessary for the original data set since it uses a 4 Hz sampling rate. For example, the eda_clean function of the NeuroKit2 Library does not filter data with a sampling rate lower than 7 Hz since high frequency noise should not be captured by such a slow sensor in the first place and instead should have been filtered out in advance by an analog filter to avoid aliasing.

Calculating Skin-Related Features To split the data into tonic and phasic components, a Butterworth filter is used. This is also the default for

Figure 14: False positive phasic activity detection when using short time windows using NeuroKit2’s `eda_process`

the NeuroKit2 library. The frequency cutoff is not defined for the original paper. The NeuroKit2 library uses a 0.05Hz cutoff by default. This adapts the method for splitting tonic and phasic components implemented in BIOPAC’s `acqknowledge` software. We assume this is what the original authors meant by saying, “we used a Butterworth filter to split the EDA signal into its tonic and phasic part.” [96, p. 2986].

EDA Algorithm: Unexpected Behavior One word of warning is needed before using our implementation for the EDA processing. When using the Neurokit2 `eda_process` function to find SCR peaks, using short windows (10-30s) like in the original study may lead to strange behavior. The algorithm might detect phasic activity in the signal where there is none, as it does not use a minimum threshold for the peak detection. As an example, we have plotted a 20-second sample (with no activity) where small peaks (probably noise) are detected as SCR Peaks (see Figure 14).

Calculating Temperature Features For temperature, we simply calculate the mean and max temperature values in a time window using the NumPy library.

Number of Calculated Features One important deviation is the final number of features we have extracted. While the original study calculates 63 features (according to a note in the conference presentation), we have only managed to identify 49 features based on the descriptions in the original paper. Additionally, as previously explained, we had to drop the five EDA features due to a measurement error, as well as not being able to use 8 features derived from proprietary EEG measures (i.e. "meditation", "attention"), finally arriving at 36 features used in the subsequent machine learning steps (**D46**). We do not know which exact features would be still missing, having tried to extract all features described in the original paper and the supplemental materials. For a comparison of calculated features see Table 10.

Normalization For normalization, the original authors record the same features for a two-minute baseline recording and then subtracts them from the features calculated for each interruption. Unfortunately, the original authors do not provide a source for this normalization method and it is unclear to us how effective this method truly is at normalizing, given the fact that in our models normalized data were still a very good predictor for guessing the individual participant. In our replication, we use only 100 instead of the full 120 seconds (i.e. two minutes) used in the original paper (**D47**). The reason for discarding the first 20 seconds was to avoid a short peak which occurs when starting recording. However, at the time of writing we have reviewed the data again and this short peak only occurs in the first fraction of a second. We speculate that this was a programming error where 20 samples (samples at 256 Hz) got confused with 20 seconds. We provide a fixed version for the replication package, but the results presented in this paper, used the 100-second-long baseline samples for the normalization steps.

Repeating Processing Steps and Combining Data The above steps have to be repeated manually for each participant's data set. After doing so, the normalized data are aggregated and exported to CSV files and ready to be used for the subsequent machine learning.

5.2.8 Recreating the Machine Learning Steps

Overview of Machine Learning Steps Recreating the machine learning steps, we had to rely solely on the descriptions from the original study. Since we did not have access to source code and/or a detailed explanation of each machine learning step, our implementation might deviate from the original (**D48**). The original study used the Weka framework for the machine learning tasks. This is a machine learning framework written in Java which is usually

Table 10: Overview of the Original and Replicated Subsets of Features. The letters in the square brackets denote which feature subsets were used after the feature subsets were used in the final models after feature selection, where "L" denotes the original lab study and "F" denotes the field study.

Original	Replication
EEG Features [L, F]	EEG Features
Power Bands ($\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \theta$)	Power Bands ($\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \theta$)
All Simple Fractions of Power Bands ($\alpha/\beta, \alpha/\gamma$, etc.)	All Simple Fractions of Power Bands ($\alpha/\beta, \alpha/\gamma$, etc.)
Two Specific Fractions of Power Bands: $\theta/(\alpha + \beta), \beta/(\alpha + \theta)$	Two Specific Fractions of Power Bands: $\theta/(\alpha + \beta), \beta/(\alpha + \theta)$
Proprietary EEG Features [L, F]	Proprietary EEG Features
Meditation: Min, Max, Mean, Standard Deviation	<i>DISCARDED</i>
Attention: Min, Max, Mean, Standard Deviation	<i>DISCARDED</i>
Eye Related Features [L, F]	Eye Related Features
Number of Eye Blinks	Number of Eye Blinks
Heart-Related Features [L, F]	Heart-Related Features
Heart Rate	Heart Rate
Heart Rate Variance	Heart Rate Variance
Number of Peaks (BVP)	<i>Number of Peaks (Deviation: ECG)</i>
Peak Amplitude (BVP): Max, Mean, Sum	<i>Peak Amplitude (Deviation: ECG): Mean, Sum</i>
SDNN	SDNN
PNN200	PNN200
PNN500	PNN500
EDA Features [L]	EDA Features
Number of SCR Peaks	<i>DISCARDED</i>
SCR Amplitude: Mean, Sum	<i>DISCARDED</i>
SCL: Mean	<i>DISCARDED</i>
AUC	<i>DISCARDED</i>
Temperature [L, F]	Temperature
Mean, Max	Mean, Max

Table 11: Summary of all deviations from the original data processing steps

ID	Deviation	Original	Replication
D42	Programming Language	MATLAB	Python (+ SciPy, NeuroKit2)
D43	Eye Blink Detection Algorithm	No Source Code; Reference to Methodology	Potential deviation in implementation of replicated of algorithm
D44	Heart Feature Extraction Algorithm	-	Potential deviation in implementation of replicated of algorithm
D45	EDA Signal Processing	-	Potential deviation in implementation of replicated of algorithm
D46	Number of Calculated Features	63	49
D47	Baseline Data Length	120 seconds	100 seconds

controlled via a provided GUI. It does also provide an API for Java code integration. It is unclear to us which steps were performed in the GUI and which steps (if any) were implemented as Java code. In our replication, we perform the following three steps manually in the Weka Explorer: 1) feature selection, 2) initial model performance validation (10-fold cross-validation) and 3) manual creation of the folds used for "per-participant" cross-validation. The cross-validations ("per-instance" and "per-participant") are implemented as Java code via the Weka API, which allowed us to have more automated control over the framework.

Algorithm Choice In the original study, the authors compare a set of different machine learning algorithms. However, there is no clear description of how this comparison was conducted. For our replication we considered three possible solutions to deal with this problem: 1) we could try to construct our own comparison method, 2) we could use a random forest classifier which in a prior study [26] on average outperformed other models when no model tweaking was involved or 3) we could simply accept the original comparison results and use a Naïve Bayes classifier for the rest of the analysis. For the scope of this master's thesis, we chose not to conduct our own comparison of various model performances, eliminating the first option. Option two was

eliminated with the reason that we wanted to replicate the results as closely to the original methods as possible, therefore, we chose to accept the original comparison results (D49).

Tuning Hyperparameters Another question was that if any of the models hyperparameters have been tuned. For our replication, we have chosen not to tune hyperparameters since it is never explicitly mentioned in the original study.

Setting Random Seed Numbers One problem with reproducibility in machine learning is the use of randomness in certain steps [12]. Unfortunately, this problem also presents itself in the original study since the seed numbers for the pseudo-random methods are not provided by the original paper, potentially having used default values. That being said, since we are not conducting a reproduction (i.e. repeating the steps on the original data) the use of a different random seed should not be as important, since using a different data set should lead to far greater deviation from the original experiment than the use of different random seeds. Nevertheless, for our replication, we specify the exact random seed we have used for all steps involving randomness.

Replicating Feature Selection We have tried replicating the feature selection by using CfsEvalSubset and ten-fold cross-validation. This resulted in a selection of only a single feature. As such, we investigated this strange behavior by running CfsEvalSubset on the whole data set since this gives more detail in the output. We then saw that the merit score returned for the optimal subsets was extremely low (merit for 10-second time window data: 2-state = 0; 5-state= 0.173), meaning that no single predictor could contribute any significant correlatedness to the target variable as calculated by CfsEvalSubset. To continue with the next steps, we chose to deviate from the original methodology and instead use a wrapper-based feature selection method (WrapperSubsetEval) wrapping around the Naïve Bayes classifier (D50), which instead selects the best subset based on the best cross-validation results of the classifier. Although achieving the original function of reducing the number of selected features, we are not sure how this affects the original goal of preventing overfitting. That being said, it is never explicitly explained in the original paper how reducing the number of features effectively reduces the risk of overfitting. On the contrary, Vabalas et al. argue that in small sample sizes, feature selection might introduce overfitting rather than reduce it [87]. Unfortunately, Larracy et al. report that using wrapper-based feature

selection might be even more prone to introducing overfitting compared filter-based methods (used in the original study), which we recognize as a potential threat to validity [47]. We discuss the problems of overfitting (regarding the study design) in more detail in Section 8.1.1.

Prepare Data for Time Window Comparison We repeat this feature selection step for all time window lengths and save each data set to be able to compare the performance of the different time window lengths, as done in the original study. The selected features are used for both the "per-instance" and the "per-participant" cross-validation.

Prepare Data for Per-Participant Cross Validation Finally, we split the data set into 10 training and 10 test sets, each time excluding one participant from the training set and taking this participant's data as the corresponding training set. These 20 additional data sets are saved so that they can be used for the "per-participant" cross-validation.

Building and Validating Prediction Models At this stage, we have prepared and saved all the necessary data sets to carry out the final model validation. As previously stated, we are not sure how exactly this was carried out. If we would like to stick to the Weka GUI, we could have potentially used the Weka experimenter. This tool allows implementing some more complicated validation methods. To reduce the number of manual steps required, we have implemented all validation steps as Java code, making use of the Weka API which exposes the algorithms usually available in the GUI. This should also make our steps more easily repeatable, compared to manual steps. Based on the reported results, we assume that the original validation used a one sample t-test where the majority classifier is a scalar baseline and the cross-validation results are the samples. The one sample t-test is also implemented directly in the Java code. At this stage of the machine learning process, we do not identify any additional deviations from the original study.

5.3 Replication Package

The materials used in the replication process are bundled in a replication package, hosted in a GitHub repository, and archived on Zenodo [10].

Table 12: Summary of all deviations from the original machine learning steps

ID	Deviation	Original	Replication
D48	Protocol / Code Implementation	-	Potential deviation in implementation of replicated of protocol/algorithm
D49	Algorithm Selection	Comparing Performances of 3 Algorithms	Accept best performing algorithm from original study
D50	Feature Selection	CfsEvalSubset (Weka)	WrapperSubsetEval (Weka)

General Overview The replication package consists of six main directories:

1. Data Processing
2. Data
3. Experiment Documents
4. Interruption App
5. JHotDraw
6. Result Analysis

License The replication package contains three types of files which may fall under copyright protection: 1) written documents (e.g. this paper, the experiment protocol, etc.), 2) source code (e.g. processing scripts), 3) data sets. All the license choices were motivated by the recommendations in the *Reproducible Research Standard* by Stodden [82, 83].

All documents are licensed under a CC BY-SA 4.0 license which only requires downstream attribution and redistribution under the same conditions. We have chosen to include a Share-Alike clause so that modified versions in future replications publish their replication packages under similar conditions.

All source code is licensed under the MIT license. As it is a "Copyleft" license without any restrictions on the use of the software, it mainly serves to limit any warranty or liability connected to the use of the software. Additionally, the bundled in JHotDraw Project comes with an MIT license since this license fits the former criterion, we chose to also use it for the rest of the replication package, so that replicators need to only deal with one type of license, keeping the package as simple as possible.

All data set are released under a Creative Commons public domain certification (CC0) to remove the possibility of any residual copyright existing in the data set (i.e. in the “original selection and arrangement”).

Data Processing: Overview Data Processing includes the following subdirectories:

1. ”Data Pre-Processing”: all the Python source code used for pre-processing (as described in Section 5.2.7)
2. ”Feature Selection and Model Building”: protocol to replicate the all manual steps in the Weka GUI as well as the Java source code for the automated steps (as described in Section 5.2.8)
3. Python source code for calculating the correlations used in the result analysis of Section 7.3
4. Python source code for the descriptive statistics used in Section 7.1.

Data Processing: Pre-Processing The Data Pre-Processing directory contains two Python scripts. Firstly, ”Baseline Feature Calculation” needs to be run first to calculate the baseline features used for the normalization step described in Section 5.2.7. Secondly, ”Feature Calculation and Normalization” is run to calculate the features from the experiment sessions and normalize them using the previously calculated baseline features. While the former is a simple Python script, the latter is a Jupyter Notebook containing additional documentation embedded as Markdown text.

Dependency Management The ”python-requirements.txt” file provides a list of dependencies with exact version, which can be used by pip to install all packages necessary to run the Python code in the ”Data Processing” directory. The Java code is built as a Maven project and includes a pom.xml file which specifies all dependencies with exact versions. The manual steps in the machine learning procedure require Weka 3.8.0 installed on your machine.

Data The Data directory includes the data used in the replication. Due to data privacy, the sensor data cannot be shared in the replication package. ECG data might be especially sensitive since they could be used to derive information about the participants’ health (e.g. heart problems). Simple pseudonymization would not have sufficed to enable the sharing of this data set, as pseudonymized data are still treated as personal data in the GDPR [81].

The interruption data do not include personal data, as such they will be shared in the replication package.

Experiment Documents The "Experiment Documents" directory contains documents which are used during the experiment session itself:

1. Two versions of the experiment protocol with detailed instructions for the experimenter
 - (a) Full version: used in the replication
 - (b) Reduced version: excluding elements added due to extension
2. Pre-Interview questionnaire
3. Post-Interview questionnaire
4. Document explaining sensor setup
5. YouTube link to fish tank movie used for baseline recording
6. PowerPoint Presentation used for task explanation and demo run of simulated interruptions
7. Document explaining hexagon geometry, which can be used by the participants during the programming task.

Interruption App The "Interruption App" directory contains the source code of the rebuilt tablet app for simulating interruption during the experiment. It contains a short tutorial of how to run and compile the code. Alternatively, a precompiled executable file is also contained in the "Releases" directory, which does not require any compilation steps.

JHotDraw The "JHotDraw 7.0.6" directory contains two versions of the project code used by the participants in the programming session (for more details on project and tasks, see Section 4.3.1); 1) a "Clean" version without any changes made, to be used as a starting point for the programming task, and 2) a "Solved" version, where the code change tasks have been implemented, to be used as a reference for the experimenters. Additionally, this directory contains the two icons ("createCircle.png" and "createHexagon.png") which can be used by the participant during the programming tasks.

Results Analysis The "Results Analysis" directory contains all spreadsheets used for the analysis of the results used in Section 7 as well as the evaluation of the pre- and post-interviews.

6 Limitations

In this chapter we discuss the consequences that the deviations from the original experiment design (described in Section 5.2) might have on the comparability of the results.

Effects of Deviating Participant Profile Having deviated from the original participant profile (see Section 5.2.2) by a lower average developing (professional/general) experience, we were expecting an impact on the perceived task difficulty and task completion. Reviewing the post-interview answers revealed that task difficulty did not increase considerably. Tasks completion, however, was impacted, both in the number of participants which completed task 1, and participants having troubles navigating the code. Both of these facts could be the result of lower average developing experience, but other factors might have also played a role such as variations in the tasks explanations or participant's familiarity with this type of code change task. We do not see the other deviations affecting the experiment outcome to a meaningful extent.

Effects of Deviating Sensor Setup: BVP vs ECG Firstly, while in terms of heart-related features the ECG sensor is even more accurate than the BVP sensor used in the original studies, features concerning the amplitude of the ECG signal might not be directly comparable with one derived from the BVP signal.

Effects of Deviating Sensor Setup: Sampling Rates Secondly, although we have used a lower sampling rate for the EEG recording, in theory this should not be a problem, since the highest frequency we are interested in ($<80\text{Hz}$) is well below the Nyquist-Shannon limit which states that aliasing occurs at frequencies higher than half of the nominal sampling rate (i.e. $256\text{Hz}/2=128\text{Hz}$) [89]. Furthermore, since the NeXus-10 MKII employs an analog anti-aliasing filter before the analog to digital converter, we can rule out aliasing as a significant factor. In practice, however, a prior study has put up far stricter safety factors between $1/5$ - $1/10$ of the nominal sampling rate, arguing that short-lived occurrences of high frequency information cannot be captured adequately by lower sample rates due to Heisenberg's uncertainty

principle when applying Fourier transformations [89]. Since we have only spotted this error after 9 of the 10 experiment sessions took place, we can only acknowledge this unwanted deviation. We have tried to measure the impact of this error by recording a session with a 1024 Hz sampling rate digitally down sampling the signal to 512 and 256 Hz and calculating the features so that we could compare each sampling rate. The calculated features varied strongly between 256 Hz and 512 Hz and higher. However, we are not sure if such a method of comparing sampling rate is adequate for this task, since we do not know how the sampling rate configuration affects the behavior of the analog anti-aliasing filter. That being said, three out of the four related works [30, 48, 55] referenced by the original paper have all used EEG sensors sampling at 256 Hz and this configuration remains popular with newly released EEG headsets (e.g. Neurosity Crown ⁹). Therefore, we assume that this deviation should not have a substantial enough effect on our results. As for the other measures (i.e. ECG, EDA, temperature), these were sampled at higher sampling rates¹⁰ (ECG: 256Hz; EDA & temperature: 32Hz) than the original 4Hz of the Empatica E3.

Effects of Deviating Sensor Setup: Ground Electrode Placement

Thirdly, in our tests, the deviating ground electrode placement successfully removed mains hum in the EEG recording. As such, we do not see this deviation significantly impacting the final result.

Effects of Deviating Sensor Setup: More Restrictive Setup

Fourthly, in comparison to the original wireless setup, having the participants connected to 8 wires might have been more distracting to the participants. That being said, when asked "How much did the fact that you were wearing the sensors influence you? (1 not at all - 5 very much)" the average answer was a score of 1,7 (close to 1="not at all"), which points to this deviation not having a large impact on the participant.

Effects of Deviating Sensor Setup: Discarding EDA

Lastly, due to a configuration error we had to discard the EDA signal. This might make the results less comparable, given the lack of a feature set. That being said, in the field study the original authors dropped the EDA features during the feature selection step, speculating that the increased noise in the field context might have reduced the usability of the signal. This would imply that, while it is

⁹<https://neurosity.co/tech-specs>

¹⁰Higher sampling rates provide a more detailed signal and therefore should not have a negative effect on the captured data.

not optimal to discard these features, the EDA signal might not be essential to recreate comparable prediction models.

Effects of Deviating Experiment Context Due to the limitations of the eye tracker the participants had to sit in a special chair in a correct posture. This might have influenced the participants' ability to fully concentrate on the tasks. To minimize the effect of this deviation, we asked each participant if they were feeling comfortable enough to program for the next 60-minute phase, before we continued to the next phase. Similarly, the lower task completion rate might have influenced how interruptible or disturbed by the notifications the participants felt during the programming session, further decreasing the comparability of our results to the original results.

Effects of Deviations in Experiment Protocol Due to a configuration error we were not able to monitor the participants precisely enough to calculate resumption and edit lag. In hindsight, we should have simply recorded screen captures of the workstation (as was done in the original study) as a fail-safe in the event where our method of capturing participant activity could have failed. This is especially true, considering the low extra effort required to add such a measure. As for the longer preparation phase and extra steps introduced by the extension (e.g. eye tracker calibration), we do not think they had any meaningful influence on the experiment's outcome.

Effects of Deviations in Interruption App Design Given the simple design of the interruption app we do not think that the deviations of possibly different fonts and notification sound had a major impact on the outcome of our experiment. Even the extra information screen added as part of the replication only required a single button press to move on, introducing a minimal amount of friction to the app design. That being said, the choice of a high-pitched notification sound might have influenced how disrupted the participants felt by the notification.

Effects of Deviations in Data Processing Given the lack of access to source code, all the data processing steps had to be rebuilt without knowledge of the specific algorithms used. This may impact comparability of the original and replicated feature set.

Effects of Deviations in Machine Learning Process Due to a lack of access to the original protocol and/or source code it is hard to assess how much the replicated machine learning steps deviate from the original study

design. Furthermore, using wrapper-based feature selection is not a perfect substitute for the filter-based feature selection used in the original and was done out only because the original method did not work properly on our data set. Both of these deviations, make it harder to compare the original and replicated results.

7 Experiment Results

This section reports the results obtained in the replication and compares them with the ones from the original study. This includes 1) descriptive statistics about the interruption data, 2) the performance of interruptibility prediction, 3) selected features for prediction, 4) correlation of interruptibility, mental load and lags, and finally 5) evaluation of the questionnaires regarding interruption timing and support.

7.1 Interruption Data

In total, we have collected 82 interruption samples from 10 participants, compared to the 72 samples from 8 participants used in the original study. First, let us compare the distribution of the interruption data. In our experiment sessions, participants were interruptible only 61% of the time. This is considerably lower than both the original lab (83.3%) and field study (71.2%) (see Figure 15). Moreover, the distribution of the 5-point scale scores looks very different to the original distribution (see Figure 16). These scores were the answers to the question of "How do you rate your interruptibility at the time of the notification?" on a scale from 1 = "Very Interruptible" to 5 = "Very Uninterruptible". While in the original lab study, the scores seem to be distributed binomially around the score 3 (i.e. undecided; neither interruptible nor uninterruptible), in our experiment it follows roughly a bimodal distribution around the scores 2 and 4 (i.e. more clearly drawing the line between being interruptible or not but also avoiding extremes). Furthermore, while in the original lab study 3 is the most popular score, in our experiment it is the least popular one.

The original paper also makes the observation that, while interruptibility scores are correlated with interruption lag, the latter follows a different distribution, namely an exponential distribution. We can confirm this observation in our experiment, where interruption lag also seems to follow an exponential distribution with half of the interruption lasting shorter than 13 seconds, while some outliers have lasted 2–6 minutes (see Figure 17). Coming back to the previously mentioned correlation between the two measures, we only saw

Figure 15: Distribution of the participants' two-state interruptibility scores during each experiment.

Figure 16: Distribution of the five-state interruptibility scores during each experiment. Colors red and blue denote "interruptible" and "not interruptible" respectively.

Figure 17: Distribution of the interruption lag of each interruption from the replicated experiment.

a weak but significant correlation ($r < 0.39, p < 0.0005$)¹¹ which matches the originally observed effect size.

7.2 Model Performance

In this section we report the results of the models built using Naïve Bayes algorithm. We discuss the rationale behind choosing this algorithm in Section 5.2.8.

¹¹We use Pearson’s r as the correlation coefficient.

In this section we frequently speak of the **”performance”** of different machine learning models or more precisely model configurations (i.e. selected time windows, features, algorithms). Although the original study never explicitly defines their performance metric, it is implicitly defined as the average accuracy which the model configuration scores in the ten times ten-fold cross-validation step. We recognize that the choice of an performance metric is not trivial (as discussed by Japkowicz [39]). However, to keep our result easily comparable with the original ones, we have decided to stick to the original authors performance metric. As such, for our results comparison we will consistently use the term **”performance”** as defined above.

7.2.1 Time Windows Comparison

To use the continuous biometric data in the machine learning models, the data have to be converted into discrete features using time windows, which ended at the moment of the interruption notification. Although prior studies have used a variety of different time window lengths ([38, 27]), no guidelines on choosing the optimal length could be found. Therefore, the original study treats time window length as an optimization parameter for the machine learning model. The original results show that shorter time windows perform slightly better, but that results do not vary strongly across different time window lengths. It finally uses the shortest time window of ten seconds for the final analysis. As such, we have replicated this parameter optimization to check if shorter time windows also perform slightly better for our data set as to provide comparable results for the rest of the analysis. The replicated results exhibited the same pattern as in the original. Therefore, the ten-second time window was also used in our final analysis.

Replicating the comparison of different time windows, we see a similar trend to the original study (compare with Figure 9), where shorter time windows seem to perform better, albeit rather small differences (see Figure 18). In fact, when conducting an ANOVA test ($\alpha = 0.05$) on the different replicated performance results for the two-state classification, time windows under 60 seconds were significantly better than longer time windows (except for the 20 seconds time window, where the difference was only significant at $\alpha = 0.1$). The difference in between the shorter windows (10–60 seconds) was not significant. For the five-state classification, the differences are quite small, so the only significant difference can be observed between the two shortest time windows (10 and 20 seconds) and the 120-second time window. In conclusion, while at least for the two-state classification, we do see a slight trend of

Figure 18: Replicating time window comparison: Classification accuracies for two and five categories using different time windows and Naïve Bayes.

shorter time windows performing better, we cannot see conclusive evidence that shorter time windows are better suited for five-state classification. The latter results are more in line with what the original authors observed in their subsequent field study. For the rest of this section, we present the results obtained using the 10 seconds time window since this configuration did result in the best performance, but also for better comparability with the original results which also used this time window.

7.2.2 Two and Five States Interruptibility

The original study asks if it is possible to predict interruptibility with high accuracy using biometric sensor data. Given the imbalance in the original data set (see Section 7.1), they compare the model accuracy to the baseline of always guessing the majority class. However, since the original research question might mislead a reader into believing that a high accuracy was achieved on a balanced data set, we compare the model performances in two ways. Firstly, we compare the absolute accuracy of the original and replicated models to see if a high accuracy can be reproduced in a more balanced data set such as ours. Secondly, we compare the relative improvement over the majority classifier baselines, as a more realistic expectation of replicated results.

The replicated results of the two-state and five-state model performance are reported in Figure 13. As in the original results (see Figure 6), both models perform significantly better at predicting interruptibility than the

States	Per Instance CV			Per Participant CV			Majority Classifier
	Accuracy	Cohen's Kappa	Stdev	Accuracy	Cohen's Kappa	Stdev	
Two	76%*	0.48	13.1	71%	0.11	16.4	60.98%
Five	46*	0.26	14.8	48%	0.22	21.6	35.37%

Table 13: Replicated results by number of states, for "per-instance" and "per-participant" cross-validation, compared to a majority classifier as a baseline (* indicates there is a significant difference in accuracy to the majority classifier)

majority classifier baseline. That being said, our model performances vary far more strongly than the original models (replication: $\pm 13.1\text{pp}$ [two-state] and $\pm 14.8\text{pp}$ [five-state] vs. original: $\pm 0.7\text{pp}$ [two-state] and $\pm 2.9\text{pp}$ [five-state]).

We were not able to reproduce such a high accuracy of over 90% as in the original study, but our data set is also far less skewed, as can be seen by the difference in majority classifier performance 60.98% vs. 83.3% (compare with Figure 15). Therefore, in terms of relative difference to the baseline accuracy, we see similar improvements at 15pp above the baseline for the two-state classification (original: +8.2pp[lab];+7.9pp [field]) and 10.63pp above the baseline for the five-state classification (original: +5pp[lab];+0.1pp [field]).

For the per-participant cross-validation, we come to the same result as the original study, with no significant improvement over the majority classifier.

We have also computed the confusion matrices for both five-state and two-state classification, as was done in the original paper. We report these in Tables 14 and 15. In the original study, the five-state classification model's error primarily comes from guessing an adjacent category (i.e. guessing two instead of three). We have observed different results in that the error follows the distribution of the interruptions (compare with Figure 16), or in other words the model tends to predict the two most popular categories two and four.

7.2.3 Feature Choice

As previously discussed in Section 5.2.8, the original method for reducing the set of features (CFSEval) did not work in our replication, therefore, we decided to use a wrapper-based method instead. Therefore, the results of this section cannot be directly compared with the original results. Nevertheless, we report the selected features in Table 16. EDA features as well as the two proprietary EEG features ("Meditation" and "Attention") had to be discarded due to reasons described in Section 5.2.3. BVP measures were substituted with ECG measures, the rationale is again described in Section 5.2.3. Compared to the feature selection done in the original study (see Figure 10) which has selected between 11 and 20 features per model, our approach selected very

Truth	Prediction	
	interruptible	not-interruptible
interruptible	43.7	6.3
not-interruptible	12.9	19.1
F-Measure	0.82	0.67

Table 14: Replication of confusion matrix for Naïve Bayes classification into two states using per instance cross-validation with individual class accuracies (F-measure). A darker background color corresponds to more prediction of this type being made rather than others (i.e. true positives was the most popular guess = darkest color; false positives was the least popular guess = lightest color etc.). Compare with confusion matrices from original experiment (see Figure 7).

Truth	Prediction				
	1	2	3	4	5
1	4.3	6	0.1	0.4	0.2
2	0.1	23.3	1.4	3.9	0.3
3	1	2	5.8	1.2	0
4	1	12.1	2	5.4	0.5
5	2	4.8	2	2.2	0
F-Measure	0.51	0.93	0.25	0.44	0.00

Table 15: Replication of confusion matrix for Naïve Bayes classification into five states using per instance cross-validation with individual class accuracies (F-measure). A darker background color corresponds to more predictions of this type being made rather than others (i.e. guessing "2" correctly was the most popular = darkest color; guessing "5" correctly was the least popular = lightest color). Compare with confusion matrices from original experiment (see Figure 8).

Sensor	Used Features
EEG	δ [2], θ/γ [2], α/γ [2,5]
ECG	Number of (r-)Peaks[2], Max. (r-)Peak Amplitude[5], IBI PNN50[5]
Temperature	Mean Temperature[2]
EDA	DISCARDED

Table 16: Replicating features selection: Features selected by wrapper-based algorithm for two-state (2) and five-state (5) classification.

few features, only selecting five features for the two-state classification and three features for the five-state classification. Our feature selection, however, covers all the sensor types (EEG, ECG (Substitute for BVP), Temperature), used in the original experiment, except for the EDA sensor data which had to be discarded due to a measurement error (see Section 5.2.3 for a detailed description of the error).

7.3 Interruptibility, Mental Load and Lags

The original experiment was interested if the claims made by Bailey et al. [8] that interruptions during high mental load moments are more disturbing would also apply in the experiment setting. To do so, they inspected correlations between interruptibility and mental load at the time of the interruption and between interruptibility and the perceived disruptiveness of the interruption. In the following we tried to replicate these correlations as well. We could only replicate a weak correlation between interruptibility and mental load. Furthermore, we could not replicate the correlation between interruptibility and disruptiveness.

On the other hand, the original authors were interested if interruption lag could be used as an objective substitute for perceived interruptibility, as proposed by Fogarty et al. [27]. To do so, the original experiment observed the correlation between the interruptibility score and interruption lag, but only observed a weak correlation between these two metrics. In our replication, we also observed a weak correlation.

To calculate the correlation coefficient, the original paper uses the Pearson correlation based on the answers to the five-point Likert scale surveys. While some of the assumptions necessary to use Pearson correlation are broken when using Likert scale data, Pearson r is not very sensitive to violation of these assumptions [63]. To have more realistic expectations about the replication results we also control, if our results fall inside the prediction interval as described by Patil et al. [67]. This method makes a number of assumptions on the distribution of sampled effect sizes which for the purposes of this

replication we take for granted since we cannot know the true distributions. As such, the prediction intervals only serve as guides of what a replicator should expect rather than exact rules.

Interruptibility and Mental Load Firstly, the original paper reports two significant and highly positive correlations. The first observed effect is between interruptibility and mental load in the lab study ($r=0.815$) and in the field ($r=0.702$). Replicating the experiment we only see a weak but significant effect ($r=0.318$; $p=0.004$). We calculate prediction intervals for the lab ($[0.674, 0.898]$) and field study ($[0.533, 0.817]$), where our observed effect falls outside both prediction intervals.

Interruptibility and Disruptiveness The second effect observed is between interruptibility and disruptiveness in the lab study ($r=0.807$) and in the field ($r=0.741$). Here we cannot replicate a significant effect in the replication ($r=0.17$; $p=0.13$). We compute the prediction intervals for the lab ($[0.661, 0.894]$) and for the field study ($[0.589, 0.843]$) and again our observed effect falls outside both intervals.

Interruptibility and Interruption Lag Next the original paper reports a weak but significant correlation between the perceived interruptibility and interruption lag in the lab ($r=0.382$, $p < 0.001$) and the field study ($r = 0.282$, $p < 0.001$). Our replication matches these results ($r=0.381$; $p=0.0004$). For completeness, we computed the prediction intervals for the lab ($[0.079, 0.620]$) and for the field study ($[0.013, 0.513]$).

7.4 Effectiveness of Negotiated Interruptions

The original study validates to what extent the negotiated interruption was used by the participants. While in the original experiment the interruption lag was used mostly as intended (e.g. to collect thoughts, finish the current task, etc.), in our experiment it was much less utilized as can be seen in the shorter average interruption lag and also in the post-interview results.

Average Interruption Lag The average interruption lag in the original experiment was 30.4 seconds (± 7.5) in the lab study, and 44.9 seconds (± 6.7) in the field study. In our replication we observe a substantially shorter average interruption lag at 28.77 seconds (± 49.68). Furthermore, our results are quite skewed due to five outliers that are 100–350 seconds long. If we remove

these outliers, the average interruption lag becomes even shorter at 17.97 seconds (± 16.83).

Usage of Negotiated Interruptions In the original study, 17 of 20¹² participants commented that they use the interruption lag to finish the current edit in most cases. When replicating the experiment, this question is asked as a closed question ("Did you often try to finish the current task in the lag before addressing the interruption? (1 never - 5 always)"). We assume that the report from the original study understands "use the interruption lag to finish the current edit in most cases" as participants answering this question with a rating above 3. If this is the case, in our experiment only 3 out of 10 people used the interruption lag in such a way. Both, the shorter average interruption lag and the survey results, imply that our participants did not make as much use of the negotiated interruptions as in the original experiments.

7.5 Interruption Timing and Support

Favorable Moments for Interruptions The original paper asks the participant to rate how much they dislike being interrupted in certain situations on a scale from one (strongly like) to five (strongly dislike). Due to using a wrong version of the interview questionnaire we worded these questions as a single open question ("When does the interruption bother you most, and when not?"). The original results indicate that interruptions in the middle of tasks are not favorable especially if the mental workload is high and the current task is difficult.

Q: When does the interruption bother you most, when not? This preference is reflected in the answers of five participants, which all mention being most bothered by interruptions while working focused or "in flow". For example, one participant answered:

"It bothers me most, *when I'm really in flow* working on something[...]. If I'm coding something and if the task I'm doing right now gets increasingly complex and I'm focused more on it, I dislike it more if I'm going to be interrupted by something." (P2)

On the other hand, one participant mentioned the exact opposite:

¹²The original study pooled together the post-interview results of the lab and field study, leading to a total of 20 participants. See Section 5.2.2 for a detail explanation of how the participant pool was replicated)

”It bothers me the most, when I’m trying to focus, so I’m in the *pre-focus time*, when I’m not fully yet in the task but I am really trying to begin it, and it [...] interrupts me [the least] [...] when I’m in focus already.” (P4)

Moreover, another participant stated that he was rarely bothered by interruptions in general:

”[Being interrupted] *rarely bothers me at all*. Usually, I really don’t care, if someone interrupts me. I have no trouble finding back to the task.” (P3)

Finally, we could identify two additional factors of unfavorable interruption timing mentioned by a single participant each were: 1) task importance and time pressure

”It bothers me most [...], when I’m working on an important task and I’m working under time pressure to get something done [...].” (P10)

and 2) long time required to handle interruption:

”I guess it bothers me *if it takes a lot of time to handle the interruption* [...]. If it takes longer than one minute to handle the interactions, then it bothers me. I think the longer I’m away from the task, the harder it gets to get into my main task again. That’s why I also didn’t perceive [the simulated] interruptions that disturbing because it only took (like) thirty seconds, so I could get back to the main task faster.” (P6)

Favorable interruption timing seems to depend on a number of different factors. Furthermore, while some preferences like not wanting to be interrupted while in deep focus, were more commonly represented, they did not apply to all participants.

Importance of In-Person Interruptions The second question addressed in the original study was about desired tool support to help participants with interruptions. Here it is first important to talk about the most common type of interruptions our participants encounter. The original study emphasizes the importance of in-person interruptions. An example for an in-person interruption would be a colleague walking up to your desk and asking you for help (as opposed to interrupting you via an email).

Q: What are you interrupted by? Our interview results revealed two larger trends among our participants. Firstly, most of our participants were interrupted by phone or computer notifications. Some examples from different participants:

”Mainly by [...] messenger apps.” (P7), ”Messages, both private or related to work [...]” (P9), ”Notifications.” (P4)

Secondly, four participants did mention being interrupted by in-person interruptions. For example:

”Colleagues asking questions, mostly, maybe also [...] scheduled calls with a client or someone, where I have to prepare something, knowing that I have to work on something else at the moment, so different stuff, but mostly colleagues or clients calling.” (P8)

However, distractions such as noise, music and side-tasks were also mentioned as possible interruptions.

Q: If there was a tool that would help you avoid unwanted interruptions, which interruptions would it help you with and how? Despite the above in-person interruptions being mentioned in the original study and in our replication, none of our participants mentioned a desire for tools helping to deal with in-person interruptions.

As for desired tool support, the most common theme was categorization and filtering of notifications based on importance. Categorization of importance could be handled automatically or manually. As an example of manual categorization, one participant mentions defining a project scope for the current task and defining all contacts involved in the project. An automatic approach mentioned by another participant was scanning the message content and categorizing it based on some model of importance. One participant also mentioned that instead of filtering, less important notifications could be delayed to a more opportune moment and that the tool could send out automatic answers indicating that the person is currently focused and will respond to the message later. Lastly, a single participant was less concerned about notifications but desired a tool similar to noise-cancelling which could help him with distracting noises such as construction-site noise.

8 Threats to Validity

In the following we discuss the threats to internal, construct and external validity which might have affected our findings and how we tried to mitigate them where possible.

8.1 Internal Validity

In the following subsection we discuss the threats to internal validity. In terms of mitigation effort, since these threats only became apparent late into the replication cycle mitigation strategies such as implementing nested cross-validation for our data analysis would have required substantial rewriting of our code and performing many more manual analysis steps and was not feasible due to time limitations and, therefore, had to be reserved for future work.

8.1.1 Problems with Small Sample Size and Overfitting

During the replication a number of problems with the original study design have surfaced, which we would like to discuss. First and foremost, the sample size of the original lab study is very small in the context of machine learning tasks. This comes as no surprise given that small sample sizes are typical of studies, where drawing samples is expensive, such as studies done in neuroimaging [5]. The original study also requires a lot of time to collect data, for example the programming sessions alone took 10 hours in total (plus 5 hours total for preparation/post-interview) and have produced only 72 usable samples.

These small sample sizes inherent to the expensive study design (in terms of time and participants compensation) make it hard to avoid overfitting, which in turn leads to overly optimistic estimation of model performance during validation, as discussed by Vabalas et al. [87]. Using simulated data Vabalas et al. inspect how strongly different validation methods are affected by small sample sizes. Looking at their results, simple k-fold (in this specific case 10-fold) cross-validation is strongly affected by small sample sizes. More specifically, sample sizes between 50 and 200 samples overestimate the true accuracy by about 15-20 percent points (above the actual 50% random guessing rate). The authors conclude that nested cross-validation provides a far more robust validation method, and that feature selection performed on the entire data set before nesting contributes to most of the bias observed in simple cross-validation.

Unfortunately, a simple apples to apples comparison is not possible between the methods described by Vabalas et al. [87] and the one used in our study. Firstly, they inspect simple k-fold cross-validation, whereas the original study uses repeated k-fold cross-validation. Secondly, they simply apply features selection on the whole data set, whereas the original study applies feature selection using 10-fold cross-validation. However, regardless of those differences, in both cases feature selection is in one form or another applied to

the whole data set. This means that, information from the validation sets can spill into the training sets via feature selection. Once this bias is introduced, applying repeated cross-validation instead of a single cross-validation should not be able to eliminate this bias. Future replications should be aware of these problems and if possible, use nested cross-validation or hold-out test validation instead, as these are far more robust to overfitting [87]. Additionally, Larracy et al. [47] provide some additional guidelines for working with small data sets, warning that even more robust methods like nested cross-validation may still be prone to overfitting depending on sample size and discriminability of the data. For small sample sizes, they recommend assessing the level of discriminability of the features.

In the light of these threats, we are not sure how much the original as well as the replicated results reflect the true predictive power in the underlying data, and how much they reflect patterns which arise from random noise in the data. In other words, we are not sure if the increases in performance over the baseline accuracy, are not simply a product of overfitting due to the bias introduced in the feature selection stage.

8.1.2 Problems with Arbitrary Two-State Split

The original study initially captures interruptibility using a five-point Likert scale (1 = "very interruptible"; 5 = "very un-interruptible"), but they also were interested in predicting two-state classification. To do this, they use a split where ratings one to three are labelled as "interruptible" and four and five are labelled as "not interruptible" (1, 2, 3 | 4, 5). This approach seems to be inspired by prior work done by Hudson et al., which is referenced in the original paper. However, this prior study uses a slightly different split (1, 2, 3, 4 | 5). Hudson et al. explain that this split is done based on anecdotal evidence where people have strong feelings about being not-interruptible but have mixed feelings about being (partially) interruptible. They then argue that the bimodal distribution of interruptibility ratings they observe in the results also hints at this effect. On the other hand, the original authors do not explicitly state the rationale behind the split they have used. Moreover, no prior studies have surveyed participants on both 2-point and 5-point scales in order to check if this matches up with how participants would intuitively do this split.

We recognize that asking separate questions for both two-state and five-state interruptibility could have increased the survey's disruptiveness. However, given how fast an additional yes or no question can be answered, we do not think it would introduce too much friction. Additionally, given the original studies strong focus on the two-state prediction it would be beneficial

not to rely on the extra assumption introduced by an arbitrary split.

8.1.3 Problems With the Originally Reported “High Accuracy”

Disregarding overfitting, which was thoroughly discussed above, the original data set (lab study) is very imbalanced with the majority class making up over 80% of the data. This means that a classifier needs to explain only a small part of the variance in order to reach accuracies above 90%. Although the original study does implicitly address this issue comparing the results to the majority classifier, ultimately it presents the results in isolation, speaking of models that achieve “high accuracy”. Furthermore, the original authors never explicitly define what constitutes high accuracy. Their use of this term for both the lab study and the field study performance implies that they mean a high accuracy compared to the majority classifier baseline since absolute accuracy (91.5% vs. 78.6%) varies strongly but is pretty consistent in terms of relative difference to the baseline (+8.2pp vs. +7.9pp).

Another problem with the class imbalance is the interpretation of the model performance considering the small sample size. In the original study the data set only has 12 samples, where the participant’s state is labeled as “interruptible”. As expected, the model performs rather poorly, predicting only 7 of these 12 samples successfully (i.e. specificity = 0.58). Again, it is hard to argue that the machine learning algorithm has truly identified meaningful patterns and has not overfitted the data onto the 12 samples of the minority class. Therefore, we again urge future research to consider the problem of dealing with potential class imbalance in their study design to enable more meaningful interpretation of the model performances.

8.1.4 Compare with Follow-Up Study

In the following subsection we want to compare the results of a follow-up study [97] done by the original authors. More precisely, we want to discuss how it compares in regard to the two problems discussed above: 1) overfitting due to small sample sizes and 2) problems with highly skewed data. We perform this comparison in order to see if the follow-up study could address some of these threats or if they are present across all previous related findings.

First it is important to mention that strictly speaking the referenced study is not a replication as defined in the background section, and the study never calls itself a replication. However, we think it is valuable to mention the results of this study since it does not only build upon the original result but also shares similar goals, and overlaps in many ways with the original study design, albeit more similar to the original field study and not the lab

study. Therefore, we compare and discuss these results as the products of a conceptual replication, applying the broader definition of Mäntylä et al. [54].

Shortly summarizing the differences between these studies, they differ in four points: 1) different interruption intervals (1-11min. vs. 10-40min.), 2) different but overlapping set of sensors (EEG + EDA + *Heart*, Temperature vs. *Heart* + Sleep Tracking + Movement + Computer Interaction), 3) different interruptibility rating scales (5-point vs. 7-point). 4) more participants (10 vs 13) over a longer time span (2.5 hours vs. 2 weeks).

The last difference meant that the follow-up study was able to collect much more data building a general model out of 2515 samples (13 participants). However, the study only reports validation results for individual models built using an average of 193 samples (± 88) per participant, which again is pretty small compared to usual machine learning tasks and closer to the sample sizes of the original study (lab: $n=72$; field: $n=139$). Moreover, overfitting bias has been observed for simulated data sets as high as 6000 samples [87]. On the one hand, it should not suffer from the bias introduced by feature selection on the whole data set before running cross-validation, as they do not perform feature selection due to using a random forest classifier. On the other hand, selecting optimal time windows for each feature (which was done based on analysis on the whole data set) might be similar to feature selection and therefore, optimistic performance bias cannot be completely ruled out again. Finally, while comparing the results of their follow-up study with the original results (and our replication results) we see similar trends that a more balanced data set leads to lower accuracy and that on average an increase of 10-15pp above the majority classifier can be reported across all studies. The big caveat that remains is the potential overfitting bias due to the small sample sizes across all studies, specific to the validation methods used.

In conclusion, we do see promising results across all mentioned studies, but are worried how much of the observed performance is due to overfitting. Future research in this field should be more mindful of how to tackle the overfitting problem in their study design (e.g. by applying nested cross-validation, or by having a completely separate test set).

8.2 Construct Validity

Although we were aiming at replicating the original study as closely as possible, differences in context, unavailability of original artifacts, and genuine mistakes have all contributed to a number of deviations from the original study design (see Section 5.2.1). Deviating too far from the original study design could impact the comparability of our results with the original study. As such, we have tried to mitigate as many deviations as possible. Additionally, in

Section 5.2 we have reported any differences that could not be prevented and finally have discussed if and how certain deviations might impact the comparability of our results (see Section 6).

8.3 External Validity

Due to sharing the original study design the replicated results share the threats to validity of the original ones, in terms of external validity. Namely, the experiments have been conducted on software developers and computer science students and might not generalize to other types of knowledge workers.

In terms of our findings, insights and lessons learned from our replication we identify the following threats. Firstly, we have performed a single replication, as such, our results might not generalize to other replication studies. For better generalizability meta-analysis across many similar studies might be necessary, as recommended by Shepperd et al. [73].

9 Discussion

In this section, we discuss how our replication results compare to the original study’s findings. Subsequently, we discuss challenges that we have experienced during the replication process and provide recommendation for future replication.

9.1 Results

9.1.1 Model Performance

Replicating the original experiments, we were able to produce machine learning models with similar performances relative to the majority-classifier baseline. However, our model performance varied far more strongly, which is not a good indicator for the robustness of our models. Additionally, given the threats to validity regarding overfitting (discussed in more detail in Section 8) we are not confident whether neither the replication nor the original studies have managed to build reliable interruptibility prediction models. Needless to say, in the future more robust studies (with big enough sample sizes and optimally with true hold out data sets for unbiased testing) will be necessary to truly evaluate the performance of interruptibility prediction using biometric sensors.

The original study discusses how the field study models achieve lower accuracy scores compared to the ones from the lab study. They argue that this might be the result of more external factors (such as noise in the sensor data),

but also consider other factors such as increased sample size and more varied participant profile. The latter factor could also be applied to our replication, which also had a more varied participant profile (see Section 5.2.2 for more detail on replicating the participant profile). However, while we agree that all these factors might play a role, we believe that most of the effect can be explained by a less skewed distribution of the interruptibility ratings, given how the relative improvement over the baseline majority prediction stays consistent over these two studies. Furthermore, the originally reported over 90% accuracy is obviously inflated by the imbalanced class distribution and is therefore not a realistic benchmark for future studies.

On the topic of the poor per-participant validation performance, we would agree with the original authors in that much more data would be needed to check whether it is possible to generalize the model to unknown participants. That being said, a larger follow-up field study has been conducted since [97], which concluded that a general model is on average outperformed by individual models. However, the follow-up study shares the potential problems regarding small sample size and overfitting, which again makes it hard to know how robust their models perform on unseen data. All in all, more robust study designs and potentially more data will be necessary to be certain of how well general models work on unknown participants.

9.1.2 Relevance of In-Person Interruption

One major difference to the original results were the type of interruptions most frequently encountered in real-life. While the original study placed a lot of emphasis on in-person interruptions, in our replication participants rarely mentioned them and focused on notifications instead. We speculate that this might be a consequence of work environments changing after the COVID pandemic which lead to reduced in-person interruptions (something which is also supported by a 2021 study carried out at Microsoft [28]). As such, future research might focus more on managing notification to minimize interruptions at inopportune moments, rather than managing in-person interruptions, as the managing the former might become more and more relevant in a work environment dominated by remote work.

9.1.3 Mental Load, Interruption Lag

Compared to the strong correlation between mental load and interruptibility reported in the original study, we could only observe a weak correlation between the two. Inspecting the post-interview results, we can see that our participants' perception of interruptibility is usually influenced by other

factors such as: 1) being close to completing a task, how long the interruption takes to address, working under time pressure (regarding important deadline). We speculate that especially time pressure might have had a greater influence on the participant's perceived interruptibility than mental workload. Many participants mentioned spending a considerable amount of time navigating the project and trying to understand the project structure. It may be that this type of work was considered not demanding in terms of mental workload, but the participants might have felt less interruptible during this activity due to the time pressure of finishing the "actual" code change task. However, it is hard to make any concrete claims about this deviation after the fact.

On the other hand, we can confirm the same type of weak correlation between interruptibility ratings and interruption lags in setups with negotiated interruptions. We also observe the originally reported differing distributions of these two metrics, and some participants have also confirmed in the post-interviews that they would always address interruptions immediately.

9.1.4 Opportune Interruption Moments

While a number of participants felt more disrupted by interruption while in focus and working on complex tasks, this preference did not apply to all participants we interviewed. One participant was bothered more while trying to get into focus (but were not easily disrupted when achieving focus). The other one was rarely bothered by interruptions at all. As a consequence, even if mental load could be measured quite accurately by biometric sensors, this accuracy might not entirely carry over to predicting interruptibility considering the different effect it has on participants' interruptibility. As such, models might have to be fine-tuned to the specific preferences of each user.

Additionally, variables not related to the mental state might influence the disruptiveness of an interruption. One of the factors mentioned by a participant was how long it takes to handle the interruption. Researchers building interruption management systems might take into consideration that short interruptions might be acceptable even in low interruptibility moments.

9.1.5 Interruptibility and Disruptiveness

We have identified two possible explanations why we could not replicate a significant correlation between interruptibility and disruptiveness. Firstly, some participants have mentioned, that they found the notification sound to be quite disruptive in general. Secondly, two other participants have mentioned that they did not find the interruptions to be very disruptive regardless of interruptibility, with the first one stating that they are not easily

disrupted by interruptions in general and with the second explaining that interruptions which take less than 30 seconds to handle do not bother them.

9.1.6 Distribution of Five-State Interruptibility

The original data followed a normal distribution with most participants answering either being undecided ("3") or only moderately interruptible ("2"). In comparison, our replicated results show a clear bi-modal distribution where participants answered mostly answering being either moderately interruptible ("2") or moderately uninterruptible ("4"). It is hard to explain what could have caused this stark difference in distribution. We speculate that variations of the task explanations and/or varying concepts of "interruptibility" could have influenced the scoring behavior.

9.1.7 Predicting Adjacent Categories

The original study makes the claim that their model their models perform more robustly since most of the five-state models errors result from guessing adjacent categories (e.g. guessing "2" instead of "3"). The replicated models do not exhibit this quality, instead most of the errors result from simply guessing the most popular categories "2" and "4". However, when looking at the distribution of the original study, this observed behavior could also apply to the original study, where the model guesses the most popular categories two and three. Therefore, despite the fact that the model errors result from choosing "adjacent categories", the models might not choose *similar* categories but rather prefer the *most popular* ones, which only happen to be adjacent in the original study.

9.2 Lessons Learned

During our replication, we have encountered a number of challenges which could to some extent have been avoided. In the following, we report all challenges we could identify and subsequently provide our recommendations how they could be avoided in future replications. For easier readability, we summarize all challenges and recommendations in Table 17. As these challenges are the result of a single replication attempt, we are aware that not all of these problems might generalize to other replications and that many other challenges might still be undiscovered.

Firstly, finding participants with the specific profile described in the original paper turned out to be quite challenging. Replicators should be aware that people that previously have accepted to participate, might suddenly

decline (**C1**). These short-term deviations can significantly alter the mean and standard deviation of controlled variables of the sample. For example, average professional experience might drop considerably if one highly experienced participant drops out. In this situation finding the exact replacement for this participant will be even more difficult, especially considering time limitations. For this reason, we recommend that replicators book more participants than necessary, focusing on the harder to replace outlier candidates rather than the one with an average profile. This way, no single cancellation should be able to deviate the target profile considerably.

To deal with time limits, we recommend searching for participants in parallel to running the experiments. This strategy has proven to be successful in our replication. However, here one word of caution is needed, running experiments in parallel with participant search might lead to some experiments taking place weeks or even a couple of months apart. In some situations, this might result in extra unaccounted context variables. For example, over a long time span room temperature might vary due to changing seasons (if the room is not air-conditioned) which might impact biometric measures like skin conductivity response [69].

The next challenge we want to discuss is how the original control variables might not be specific enough to ensure a close enough replication of the original context (**C2**). While controlling for developing experience and during our post-interviews, we noticed that many participants have not been using Java recently. Furthermore, many personal contacts declined to participate, stating lack of familiarity with Java as the reason. As such, we investigated reasons why this problem occurred in our study, while it did not seem to be a problem for the original authors. On a first look, the popularity of Java among developers is not a constant. In fact, Java popularity has been in a steady decline for the past few years (see Figure 19). That being said, Java continues to rank top 3 in popularity, so it is by no means a bad choice [92]. However, if this trend continues, finding graduate students with enough Java experience might be challenging for future replications. Participants focusing on Java syntax rather than on higher level concepts might influence the way participants interact with the project tasks in comparison to the original study. On the one hand, this trend matches the popularity of Java and Python in introductory programming courses at (US) universities (CS1) as revealed by a survey done by Siegfried et al. [77]. On the other hand, according to the same survey, Java is still by far the most popular programming language in CS1 courses despite the latest downward trends. Therefore, our challenges with finding participants with enough Java expertise might not be entirely explained by the popularity of Java among university students. It may however be partially explained by the talent pool website we have used to

find participants, which anecdotally is more popular among Data Science students. In contrast, Data Science is by far dominated by R and Python in introductory courses [20] In hindsight it might have been better to control for experience with using Java rather than asking the participants about their general developing experience. Replicators might want to introduce more specific control variables in order to properly replicate the original context.

The third challenge resulted from using different hardware compared to the original study. More specifically, while the original experiment used consumer-grade sensors, we had access to lab-grade hardware. Although lab-grade hardware promises better signal quality, it can be more complex to configure and use (**C3**). For example, while the electrodes were integrated in the original hardware, in our hardware these were extra components. This allowed for the possibility of measurement errors by choosing the wrong type of electrodes, as was the case in our experiment. To avoid this problem, we recommend using the original hardware or at least the same type of hardware (e.g. consumer-grade) as used in the original experiment. If this is not possible, replicators should be aware that this change will cause more potential sources of measurement error. This type of problem will be more likely met when replicating older studies, where deprecated software and discontinued hardware might force replicators to deviate from the original sensors.

Tackling this problem from a different perspective, assistance from a trained technician in the form of an extra validation step (during the test or pilot run) might have also weeded out this sort of problem. Therefore, implementing such services might be beneficial for university labs trying to foster replication studies.

Another problem was the frequent use of default (or undisclosed) variables in the original experiment (**C4**). Optimally, we would advocate for replication packages or inquiring about the source code from the original authors. However, if the original source code is not available anymore, we advise paying close attention to default variables, especially when porting the algorithms to a different technology. For example, while the MATLAB's signal library was ported to SciPy, default parameters for the `pwelch` function had major differences which would have made replication results less comparable.

Another major challenge had to do with the replication process, namely, a number of threats to validity only emerged late into the replication process (**C5**). Some of those problems could have been avoided quite easily if they were recognized earlier (e.g. using wrong electrodes), while others would have required substantial changes to the study design even if caught early on (e.g. study design with small sample sizes leading to complicated bias prone validation - see Section 8.1.1). While the pilot study which we performed

caught some errors in advance, we did not replicate all data analysis steps at this stage. This could have caught a lot more errors prior to conducting the proper experiments. Therefore, we recommend already pretesting as many steps as possible during the pilot study with a heavy focus on identifying threats to internal validity. Here also the words of warning by Shepperd et al. [73] might have been good advice to follow, which say that replicators should pay close attention to threats to validity of the original study design, even before attempting replication, and that exact replication alone might fail to improve the validity of an underpowered original study.

We found that, direct communication with the original authors is crucial for replications. Although we were lucky to get responses from the original authors via e-mail, we can confirm the challenges reported by Shull et al. [74], where even with as many artifacts (or lab packages) available as possible, a lot of tacit knowledge will be still unavailable, and while e-mails were good at answering well-prepared and focused questions, they were not good at communicating harder to grasp gaps in knowledge about the experiment context and procedural details (**C6**). Therefore, we would recommend replicators to meet with the original authors, if possible, in a workshop setting to enable transfer of tacit knowledge. If this is not possible, replicators should be aware that thorough preparation before e-mail contact will be crucial as the original experimenters will potentially only answer clearly formulated questions. Here again repeated pilot studies could help to prepare for e-mail communication since many knowledge gaps only become apparent after carrying out the replication process.

Lastly, we encountered the problem of having the wrong version of an artifact being supplied by the original authors (i.e. wrong questionnaire) (**C7**). This only became apparent after doing the final comparison of our replication results against those from the original study. Therefore, we advise replicators not to assume that the supplied artifacts must always be correct and to double-check if they match the descriptions from the original paper. Furthermore, here again replicating all steps in the pilot study including results comparison (as far as is possible) could have helped catch this mistake early in the replication process. Here again a workshop setting instead of e-mail communication could have also avoided this mistake, as the original authors could have seen the wrong artifact version being used.

ID	Challenge	Recommendation
C1	Accounting for unexpected cancellation while replicating participant profiles.	Run participant search in parallel with experiments (Warning: Might cause experiments being more spaced apart. Could lead to extra context variables.).
		Book more participants than necessary, especially considering outliers since they influence the average more strongly.
C2	Original control variables were not specific enough and allowed for variance in participant profile between original and replication.	Consider introducing extra control variables to properly replicate the original context.
C3	Using lab-grade devices instead of consumer-grade devices leads to more potential sources of error due to more configuration options.	Optimally: Avoid changes in hardware or type of hardware. Realistically: Carefully study new configuration steps introduced by differing hardware.
C4	Default behavior of the algorithm might differ in a port to another system.	Pay close attention to the default values of algorithms when using ports.
C5	Errors and threats to validity might emerge only late into the replication process.	Run a pilot experiment replicating all steps (incl. data analysis), staying critical of the original study design, to catch threats as early as possible.
C6	Communication with original authors might be difficult. E-mail communication is not ideal for transferring tacit knowledge.	Optimally: Communicate with original authors in-person (e.g. workshop setting). Realistically: Prepare well before each e-mail communication. Insights from a thorough pilot study can help prepare properly.
C7	Supplied artifacts might be faulty or deprecated.	Always double check if artifacts resemble the description in the original paper.

Table 17: Summary of challenges encountered during the replication process and recommendations of how to deal with them.

Figure 19: Comparison of Java and Python popularity in terms of amount of posted Stack Overflow questions. [80]

10 Conclusion

In this work, we set out to replicate the findings of Züger et al. [96], in which they predicted the interruptibility of software developers with high accuracy using psycho-physiological sensors. While the original study consisted of two studies, a lab and field study, our study replicated the former.

Since the original study did not have a replication package available, we have replicated the original design as closely as possible using the descriptions from the original paper and by contacting the original authors in three rounds of Email communication, at the time of completing this manuscript. Despite our and the original authors' best efforts, certain questions about the original design remain unanswered. We provide the recreated replication package in a GitHub repository archived on Zenodo [redacted].

Using the replicated experimental design, we conducted a lab study in which we captured the psycho-physiological data of ten participants for a total of ten hours. Using a Naïve Bayes classifier, we were able to produce models, which perform significantly better than the majority classifier. However, the accuracy of the models produced varied very strongly across the cross-validation runs, therefore we are not confident that these models will generalize well to unseen data.

Furthermore, the small sample sizes, the use of unbalanced data sets, as well as the arbitrary split used to calculate the two-state labels pose a threat to validity which is inherent to the original experiment design, but also affect the validity of the replication. As a result, neither the original nor the replicated results provide enough evidence for the predictive strength of this set of psycho-physiological sensors for predicting interruptibility. Therefore, future replications must address these issues, if they want to effectively investigate the prediction of interruptibility.

We did not find the strong correlation between interruptibility and mental load that was observed in the original study. This could possibly be explained by the deviating participant profile and its effect on task completion.

Our interviews resulted in much less emphasis on direct interruptions from coworkers with none of the participant expressing a desire for tool support for this type of interruption. We speculate that this might be the result of post-COVID work environments reducing the impact of in-person interruptions.

We have identified a number of challenges which occurred during our replication. The first challenge of finding participants was specific to studies involving human subjects, while the other challenges were more generally applicable. A number of challenges could have been avoided by running pilot studies which replicate the whole study process (i.e. starting with preparation

and ending with comparison of results) and focus on internal validity of both the replication and the original study. We also identified challenges in communication with the original authors via email, namely the difficulty of transferring tacit knowledge.

As part of future work, we plan to communicate the results including the threats to validity to the original authors found. At this point, we would also like to thank the original authors for helping us with the replication process. Firstly, we would like to thank Manuela Züger for collecting and sharing as much information and resources from the original experiment as possible. We do not take for granted, that she helped us to replicate her study, even after 8 years since its publication and also after she left academia to pursue a career in industry. Secondly, we would also like to thank her supervisor, Thomas Fritz, for helping us get in touch with her.

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